

A Proof Frame for Riemann Hypothesis

Jin-Liang Wang

College of science, Qingdao University of Technology, Shandong, China (266520).

E-mail: wangjinliang0811@126.com ORCID: 0000-0002-4328-4598

Abstract

The Riemann hypothesis is a well-known mathematical problem that has been in suspense for 167 years. Its difficulty lies in the fact that the related Xi function (which shares some nontrivial zeros with the Zeta function) is involved in an infinite integral which includes infinite series with complex variable. To detour this is in vain, since all the messages are hid in it. To interpret them, there is a totally new idea, that is, to deduce an explicit symmetric formula for it. This is achieved by making prior estimations and generalizing the Gamma function. A total of three formulas are derived. Particularly, the third one in form of infinite series not only approaches the known zero-points with extremely high precision, but also meets the requirements of theoretical derivation. A possible proof frame for Riemann hypothesis is constructed by this. The missing parts are related to the complex calculations of combination numbers. Maybe the artificial-intelligence (AI) softwares are helpful. I look forward to the researchers working together to complete the proof. In addition, a possible distribution law of zero-points on the critical line was also found.

Keywords: Riemann hypothesis, Riemann Zeta function, zero point, general Gamma function, combination number.

1. Introduction

The Riemann hypothesis is a well-known mathematical problem. To crack it, just as reported by New Scientist in [1], “*unless with a totally new idea!*” To read through the monographs in [2–4] and the popular readings in [5, 6], one can find the difficulty of Riemann hypothesis lies in the complexity of the Xi function which shares the same nontrivial zeros with the Zeta function. Essentially, it is involved in an infinite integral which includes infinite series with complex variables. To detour this infinite integral is in vain, since all the messages are hid in it. To interpret them, in my brain many ideas appeared and died during the past 7 years. Among them there is only one which survives and could be seen as “a totally new idea”, that is “to remove the integral and deduce an explicit symmetric formula”! Notice that the present article may become the cornerstone of subsequent research by others, a whole story will be told.

This problem was left by German mathematician Bernhard Riemann (1826-1866) in 1859 [4, 7, 8]. He found that the distribution of prime numbers among all natural numbers is very closely related to the analytic continuation of the following infinite series on complex plane \mathbb{C} :

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = \frac{1}{1^s} + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \dots \quad (1.1)$$

with $s = \sigma + it$, which is usually called *Riemann Zeta* function. This series converges only for the case $\sigma > 1$, so all the mentioned $\zeta(s)$ below should be understood in the sense of analytic continuation. If there is a s_0 which satisfies $\zeta(s_0) = 0$, then we call it one zero point of $\zeta(s)$. This function has real zero points at the negative even integers $-2, -4, -6 \dots$ and one refers

to them as the *trivial zero points*. Relatively, the other complex zero points of it are called the *nontrivial zero points*.

Riemann hypothesis: *All the nontrivial zero points of $\zeta(s)$ have real part $\sigma = 1/2$.*

Is it true? In the official millennium problem description [9], E. Bombieri had reviewed that, in 1986 the first 1.5×10^9 nontrivial zero points of $\zeta(s)$ (arranged by increasing positive imaginary part) had been checked by J. Lune et al with numerical approach in [10], and the result showed that they are simple and all possess real part $\sigma = 1/2$. More zero points had been checked by the followers, the same thing occurred. Till now the known record was set by X. Gourdon in 2004 [11], 10^{13} zero points. So the Riemann hypothesis is very likely true. What lacks is the theoretical proof.

The analytic continuation for $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-s}$ (defined on $\sigma > 1$) is not unique. Among them, the most popular one is given by:

$$\zeta(s) = \frac{\pi^{s/2}\xi(s)}{(s-1)\Gamma(s/2+1)}, \quad (1.2)$$

which is meromorphic on \mathbb{C} with a unique pole at $s = 1$ (its residual is 1) [2–4]. Here

$$\Gamma(s/2+1) = \int_0^{\infty} x^{s/2} e^{-x} dx \quad (1.3)$$

with a default requirement $\sigma/2 + 1 > 0$. Its analytic continuation to the negative direction is done by $\Gamma(s/2) = \Gamma(s/2+1)/(s/2)$ step by step. In this sense, $-2, -4, -6 \dots$ are the zero points of $1/\Gamma(s/2+1)$, and this is why they are the trivial zero points of $\zeta(s)$. Naturally, the function $\xi(s)$ satisfies the inverse relation which was written down by Riemann:

$$\xi(s) = (s-1)\pi^{-s/2}\Gamma(s/2+1)\zeta(s)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{s(s-1)}{2} \pi^{-s/2} \Gamma(s/2) \zeta(s) \\
&= \frac{s(s-1)}{2} \left[\frac{1}{s(s-1)} + \int_1^\infty \varphi(x) (x^{s/2-1} + x^{-(s+1)/2}) dx \right] \\
&= \frac{1}{2} - \frac{s(1-s)}{2} \int_1^\infty \varphi(x) (x^{s/2-1} + x^{-(s+1)/2}) dx \tag{1.4}
\end{aligned}$$

with $\varphi(x) = \sum_{n=1}^\infty e^{-n^2\pi x}$, which satisfies a peculiar relation below (see the deduction in [12, 13]):

$$2\varphi(x) + 1 = x^{-1/2} [2\varphi(x^{-1}) + 1]. \tag{1.5}$$

Notice that $\varphi(x)$ is positive and exponentially decreasing on the interval $[1, \infty)$, the integral in (1.4) is finite and hence $\xi(s)$ is analytic on \mathbb{C} . Particularly, the zero points of $\xi(s)$ coincide with the nontrivial zero points of $\zeta(s)$, and the exploring of Riemann hypothesis can be converted to considering $\xi(s)$. To substitute s by $1-s$ the expression maintains unchanged, so $\xi(s) = \xi(1-s)$. This symmetric property implies the most important relation between the function $\zeta(s)$ and the *critical line* $\sigma = 1/2$. Correspondingly, the complex region with $0 \leq \sigma \leq 1$ is called the *critical strip* which includes all the zero points of $\xi(s)$.

In fact, $\xi(s)$ has no zero points outside the critical strip. With the aid of Euler formula:

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^\infty n^{-s} = \prod_p (1 - p^{-s})^{-1} \tag{1.6}$$

(where the last expression is a product respect to all the prime numbers $p = 2, 3, 5, \dots$), one can easily checked that $|\zeta(s)| \neq 0$, that is $|\xi(s)| \neq 0$, for the case $\sigma > 1$ (see [5]). Furthermore, the relation $\xi(s) = \xi(1-s)$ indicates that the same thing is true for $\sigma < 0$.

We note that, as the *critical strip* concerned, the two boundaries $\sigma = 1$ and $\sigma = 0$ can be gotten rid of. As reviewed in [4, 13], the proof given by de la Vallée Pousson in 1899 for this is very complex. Yet, as our approach concerned, it doesn't matter.

To denote $\xi(\sigma + it) = U(\sigma, t) + iV(\sigma, t)$, then it follows from the well-known Reflection Principle $\overline{\xi(\bar{s})} = \xi(s)$ of complex conjugate that $U(\sigma, t) - iV(\sigma, t) = U(\sigma, -t) + iV(\sigma, -t)$. Meanwhile, the relation $\xi(s) = \xi(1 - s)$ yields $U(\sigma, t) + iV(\sigma, t) = U(1 - \sigma, -t) + iV(1 - \sigma, -t)$. Based on these two relations, the symmetric properties of $\xi(s)$ are clarified as:

Lemma 1.1. *To denote $\xi(\sigma + it) = U(\sigma, t) + iV(\sigma, t)$, then its real part and imaginary part separately satisfy the symmetries and anti-symmetries bellow:*

$$\begin{aligned} U(\sigma, -t) &= U(\sigma, t), & V(\sigma, -t) &= -V(\sigma, t), \\ U(1 - \sigma, t) &= U(\sigma, t), & V(1 - \sigma, t) &= -V(\sigma, t). \end{aligned}$$

For the particular cases with $t = 0$ and $\sigma = 1/2$, the relations for V read $V(\sigma, 0) = -V(\sigma, 0)$ and $V(1/2, t) = -V(1/2, t)$. So $V(\sigma, 0) = V(1/2, t) = 0$. This indicates that the values of $\xi(\sigma + it)$ are real on the lines $t = 0$ and $\sigma = 1/2$. This lemma can be understood as: *U and V are symmetric and anti-symmetric about the two lines $t = 0$ and $\sigma = 1/2$, respectively.* That is why most of the arguments are about the upper quarter strip with $1/2 \leq \sigma \leq 1$ and $t > 0$. Particularly, due to the direct relationship with the Riemann hypothesis, the line $\sigma = 1/2$ has drawn much attention.

It is enlightening to divide Riemann hypothesis into three progressive propositions (see [5], pages 22–23):

Proposition 1.1. *In the region bounded by $0 \leq \sigma \leq 1$ and $0 < t < T$, the number of zero points of $\xi(s)$ is about $T/2\pi \log(T/2\pi e)$.*

Proposition 1.2. *On the critical line $\sigma = 1/2$ with $0 < t < T$, the number of zero points of $\xi(s)$ is also about $T/2\pi \log(T/2\pi e)$.*

Proposition 1.3. *All the zero points of $\xi(s)$ are on the critical line $\sigma = 1/2$.*

Till now only the first proposition had been proved. It was finished by German mathematician Hans von Mangoldt in 1905 [14, 4, 5]. His estimation for the zero-points number of $\xi(s)$ is

$$N(T) = \frac{T}{2\pi} \log \frac{T}{2\pi e} + O(\log(T)), \quad (1.7)$$

which is understood as taking the integer part. We note that, $O(\log(T))$ does not imply the existence of a term $C \log(T)$ for some constant C . Its meaning is that $|N(T) - (T/2\pi) \log(T/2\pi e)| \leq C \log(T)$. In fact, the previously mentioned checks are done according to this theoretical result, and the numerical approximate values for the first 10 zero points are

$$\begin{aligned} &1/2 + 14.1347251i, & 1/2 + 21.0220396i, \\ &1/2 + 25.0108575i, & 1/2 + 30.4248761i, \\ &1/2 + 32.9350615i, & 1/2 + 37.5861781i, \\ &1/2 + 40.9187190i, & 1/2 + 43.3270732i, \\ &1/2 + 48.0051508i, & 1/2 + 49.7738324i. \end{aligned} \quad (1.8)$$

On the aspect of theoretical study, in 1914 Hardy firstly proved that, *there are infinitely many zero points of $\xi(s)$ on the critical line $\sigma = 1/2$* (see the

review in [3]). Due to the efforts of Selberg [15], Levinson [16] and Conrey [17], the ratio was lifted step by step. Now the known optimal estimation is that *more than 40% of zero points of $\xi(s)$ are on the critical line $\sigma = 1/2$* (they are also simple ones). These indicate that **Proposition 1.2** is far from settled. In addition, as reviewed in [4], “*All the zero points of $\xi(s)$ are simple ones*” already became an accompanying conjecture to Riemann hypothesis.

The above survey is about the known knowledge of Riemann hypothesis, and the next is about our new findings. It is helpful for grasping the characteristics of the known zero points on the critical line. So we begin with investigating them.

2. A Possible Distribution Law for the Known Zero Points on the Critical Line

On the critical line $\sigma = 1/2$, the values of $\xi(s)$ are real (ensured by Lemma 1.1), that is, only the real part $U(1/2, t)$ of $\xi(1/2 + it)$ is left. To recall the expression of $\xi(s)$ in (1.4), it follows from [3, 4] that

$$\begin{aligned} U(1/2, t) &= (s-1)\pi^{-\frac{s}{2}}\Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2}+1\right)\zeta(s)|_{s=1/2+it} \\ &= -\frac{1+4t^2}{8}\pi^{-\frac{s}{2}}\Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2}\right)\zeta(s)|_{s=1/2+it} \\ &= -a(t)e^{i\vartheta(t)}\zeta\left(\frac{1}{2}+it\right), \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

in which

$$\begin{aligned} a(t) &= \frac{1+4t^2}{8}\pi^{-1/4}\exp\left[\Re\log\Gamma\left(\frac{1+2ti}{4}\right)\right], \\ \vartheta(t) &= \Im\log\Gamma\left(\frac{1+2ti}{4}\right) - \frac{t}{2}\log\pi \\ &= \frac{t}{2}\log\frac{t}{2\pi e} - \frac{\pi}{8} + \frac{1}{48t} + \frac{7}{5760t^3} + \cdots. \end{aligned} \tag{2.2}$$

Here \Re and \Im mean taking of real and imaginary parts, respectively. Notice that $a(t) > 0$, the zero points on the critical line are only determined by the sign shift of $Z(t) = e^{i\vartheta(t)}\zeta(1/2 + it)$. Furthermore, as reviewed in [4], the inverse expression can be employed to make the estimation [the zero points of $\zeta(1/2 + it)$ coincide with that of $\xi(1/2 + it)$]:

$$\zeta(1/2 + it) = e^{-i\vartheta(t)}Z(t) = Z(t)\cos\vartheta(t) - iZ(t)\sin\vartheta(t), \quad (2.3)$$

According to this, for the first time, Gram calculated the first 15 zero points in 1903. His method is an estimation approach based on $\sin\vartheta(t) = 0$, which yields the known *Gram points* at $\vartheta(t_k) = k\pi$ with an approximation:

$$\frac{t_k}{2} \log \frac{t_k}{2\pi e} - \frac{\pi}{8} = k\pi, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots \quad (2.4)$$

Certainly, to estimate the location of a zero point, the change of $Z(t)$ should be also considered. This adds the complexity. By the way, 29 years later, the approximate approach for $Z(t)$ was improved. The more effective approach was discovered by Siegel in 1932 among Riemann's private papers. It is known as the Riemann-Siegel formula (see page 33 of [4]):

$$Z(t) = 2 \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{1}{n^{1/2}} \cos[\vartheta(t) - t \log n] + \frac{e^{-\pi t/2 - i\vartheta(t)}}{(2\pi)^{1/2 + it} e^{-\pi i/4} (1 - ie^{-\pi t})} \int_{C_N} \frac{(-x)^{-1/2 + it} e^{-Nx}}{e^x - 1} dx. \quad (2.5)$$

where C_N is a positively oriented closed contour containing all of the points $\pm 2\pi Ni, \pm 2\pi(N-1)i, \dots, \pm 2\pi i$ and 0.

Though the method given by Gram is so rough, it is enlightening. The distribution of zero points on the critical line $\sigma = 1/2$ may possess some kind

of periodicity. In fact, for some given $t = T$, the argument $\vartheta(T)$ obtained on the critical line and the zero-points number $N(T)$ in the region $0 \leq \sigma \leq 1$ and $0 < t < T$ have close relationship:

$$\begin{aligned}\vartheta(T) &= \frac{T}{2} \log \frac{T}{2\pi e} - \frac{\pi}{8} + \dots, \\ N(T) &= \frac{T}{2\pi} \log \frac{T}{2\pi e} + \frac{7}{8} + \dots.\end{aligned}$$

Exactly, as reviewed in [3] (page 132–134), in 1918 Backlund had revealed that, for all $T \geq 2$,

$$|N(T) - \pi^{-1}\vartheta(T) - 1| < 4.350 + 0.137 \log T + 0.443 \log \log T.$$

Enlightened by this, we have a new idea. **Proposition 1.2** holds true provided that $U(1/2, t) = \xi(1/2 + it)$ can be expressed in the following form:

$$U(1/2, t) = A(t) \sin \left(\frac{t}{2} \log \frac{t}{2\pi e} + \alpha + \varepsilon(t) \right), \quad (2.6)$$

where $A(t)$, α and $\varepsilon(t)$ are the amplitude (> 0), initial phase angle and small perturbation function. Certainly, for the case with $t = 2\pi$ we have $(t/2) \log(t/2\pi e) = -\pi$. Hence, a suitable phase angle α should be chosen to accord with the fact that $\xi(1/2 + 2\pi i) = U(1/2, 2\pi) > 0$ (since $\xi(0) = -\zeta(0) = 1/2$ and there is no zero points for $0 \leq t \leq 14$, see [3], page 31). If $U(1/2, t)$ is indeed in such a periodic form, the thing becomes very simple. All the zero points on the critical line $\sigma = 1/2$ can be solved one by one with the following formula:

$$\frac{t_k}{2} \log \frac{t_k}{2\pi e} + \alpha + \varepsilon(t_k) = k\pi, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots. \quad (2.7)$$

By the way, to count the number of zero points this equation can be used in a reverse way, that is,

$$N = \frac{t_N}{2\pi} \log \frac{t_N}{2\pi e} + \frac{\alpha}{\pi} + \frac{\varepsilon(t_N)}{\pi},$$

which accords with **Proposition 1.2**. Relative to Gram's approximation in (2.4), this formula is closer to the truth. In the following we give some numerical evidences for this.

To neglect the perturbation term $\varepsilon(t_k)$ and make fitting with the known numerical approximate values t_k^* to the zero points (provided by Odlyzko in [18]), it leads to the results in **Figure 1**. To adopt the definition of standard deviation:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n (t_k - t_k^*)^2},$$

the first 50 zero-points fitting with $\alpha = \pi$, $\alpha = 4\pi/3$ and $\alpha = 5\pi/3$ yields $\sigma = 1.1725$, 0.5078 and 0.9627 . Relatively, $\alpha = 4\pi/3$ accords with the smallest standard deviation, and it is an optimal phase angle. The k -th zero point on the critical line is very close to the solution of

$$\frac{t_k}{2} \log \frac{t_k}{2\pi e} + \frac{4}{3}\pi = k\pi, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots \quad (2.8)$$

This may be a distribution law of the zero points.

The check in **Figure 2** with 10,000 zero points shows that the above distribution law is also obeyed. The error is small. Though the value of t_k^* is up to 9,877, except the 14-th and 64-th zero points, all the corresponding errors satisfy $|t_k - t_k^*| < 1$. In addition to the perturbation term $\varepsilon(t_k)$, these errors may also partly ascribe to the numerical scheme for t_k^* , though its

Figure 1: The upper sub-figure: the fitting curve with the known numerical approximate values t_k^* of the first 50 zero points, according to the formula in (2.7) with $\alpha = 4\pi/3$ and $\varepsilon(t_k) \equiv 0$. The lower sub-figure: the variation of the errors $t_k - t_k^*$ with respect to $\alpha = \pi$, $\alpha = 4\pi/3$ and $\alpha = 5\pi/3$.

Figure 2: The variation of the error $t_k^* - t_k$ with respect to the first 10,000 zero points.

calculation accuracy is up to 10^{-9} . Not forget that, essentially, the calculation of $\xi(s)$ is involved in an infinite integral which includes infinite series with complex variables. At least, the approximate values for the 14-th and 64-th zero points are questionable. To take the 14-th zero as an example. $t_{14}^* = 60.831778525$, $t_{15}^* = 65.112544048$ and hence

$$\frac{t_{15}^*}{2} \log \frac{t_{15}^*}{2\pi e} - \frac{t_{14}^*}{2} \log \frac{t_{14}^*}{2\pi e} \approx 43.5681 - 38.6353 = 4.9328 > \pi. \quad (2.9)$$

Yet, it follows from $N(T) \approx \pi^{-1}(T/2) \log(T/2\pi e)$ that, to add one π means to add a zero point. This indicates that 4.9328 is a too big difference between two adjacent zero points, it should be understood as a calculation error. With this understanding, the departure from the newly-found distribution law caused by the perturbation term $\varepsilon(t_k)$ may be smaller than the difference of $|t_k^* - t_k|$ depicted here.

Further check is given in Figure 3. This law is also obeyed for the zero points numbered from 99,900 to 100,000.

Figure 3: The comparison between the solutions of (2.8) and the approximate values t_k^* of the zero points numbered from 99,900 to 100,000.

3. To Convert $\xi(s)$ into a New Form

From this section we start theoretical research. The default domain is the upper critical strip $D = \{(\sigma, t) | 0 \leq \sigma \leq 1, 0 < t < \infty\}$. Notice that the 2-terms expression for $\xi(s)$ in (1.4) is awkward for use, we adopt the single-term form in [3] (see pages 16–17). Its deduction process is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\xi(s) &= \frac{1}{2} - \frac{s(1-s)}{2} \int_1^\infty \varphi(x) [x^{s/2-1} + x^{-(s+1)/2}] dx \\
&= \frac{1}{2} - \frac{s(1-s)}{2} \int_1^\infty \left\{ \varphi(x) \left[\frac{x^{s/2}}{s/2} + \frac{x^{(1-s)/2}}{(1-s)/2} \right] \right\}' dx \\
&\quad + \frac{s(1-s)}{2} \int_1^\infty \varphi'(x) \left[\frac{x^{s/2}}{s/2} + \frac{x^{(1-s)/2}}{(1-s)/2} \right] dx \\
&= \frac{1}{2} + \frac{s(1-s)}{2} \varphi(1) \left[\frac{2}{s} + \frac{2}{1-s} \right] \\
&\quad + \int_1^\infty \varphi'(x) [(1-s)x^{s/2} + sx^{(1-s)/2}] dx
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{1}{2} + \varphi(1) + \int_1^\infty \varphi'(x)[(1-s)x^{s/2} + sx^{(1-s)/2}]dx \\
&= \frac{1}{2} + \varphi(1) + \int_1^\infty x^{3/2}\varphi'(x)[(1-s)x^{(s-1)/2-1} + sx^{-s/2-1}]dx \\
&= \frac{1}{2} + \varphi(1) + \int_1^\infty \{x^{3/2}\varphi'(x)[-2x^{(s-1)/2} - 2x^{-s/2}]\}' dx \\
&\quad - \int_1^\infty [x^{3/2}\varphi'(x)]'[-2x^{(s-1)/2} - 2x^{-s/2}] dx \\
&= \frac{1}{2} + \varphi(1) + 4\varphi'(1) \\
&\quad + 2 \int_1^\infty [x^{3/2}\varphi'(x)]' x^{-1/2}[x^{s/2} + x^{(1-s)/2}] dx \\
&= 2 \int_1^\infty [x^{3/2}\varphi'(x)]' x^{-1/2}[x^{s/2} + x^{(1-s)/2}] dx \\
&:= 2 \int_1^\infty F(x)[x^{s/2} + x^{(1-s)/2}] dx. \tag{3.1}
\end{aligned}$$

in which $1/2 + \varphi(1) + 4\varphi'(1) = 0$ is deduced by taking the derivative of the relation (1.5). Here the superscript “ ’ ” means taking the conventional derivative, and

$$\begin{aligned}
F(x) &= \left[x^{\frac{3}{2}}\varphi'(x) \right]' x^{-\frac{1}{2}} \\
&= \frac{3}{2}\varphi'(x) + x\varphi''(x) \\
&= \frac{3}{2} \sum_{n=1}^\infty (-n^2\pi)e^{-n^2\pi x} + x \sum_{n=1}^\infty (-n^2\pi)^2 e^{-n^2\pi x} \\
&= \sum_{n=1}^\infty n^2\pi \left(n^2\pi x - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-n^2\pi x} := \sum_{n=1}^\infty a_n(x). \tag{3.2}
\end{aligned}$$

Since for all $n \geq 1$ and $x \geq 1$ the inequality $n^2\pi x - 3/2 > 0$ always holds, we have $F(x) > 0$. It follows from (3.1) that

$$U(\sigma, 0) = \xi(\sigma) = 2 \int_1^\infty F(x)[x^{\sigma/2} + x^{(1-\sigma)/2}] dx > 0 \tag{3.3}$$

for all $0 \leq \sigma \leq 1$. Particularly, in case $\sigma = 1/2$ it accords with the documented result $\xi(1/2) = -\zeta(1/2) > 0$ in [3] (see page 122).

Due to the existence of the exponential function $e^{-n^2\pi x}$, the general term $a_n(x)$ decreases sharply along with the increasing of n and x on $[1, \infty)$. The main term of $F(x)$ is the first one $a_1(x)$. Numerical simulations in Figure 4 show that the magnitude of $\sum_{n=3}^{\infty} a_n(x)$ is much smaller than that of $a_1(x)$ and $a_2(x)$.

Figure 4: The variations of $a_1(x)$, $a_2(x)$ and $\sum_{n=3}^{5000} a_n(x)$.

It is easily checked that the positive infinite series:

$$\frac{F(x)}{a_1(x)} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{a_n(x)}{a_1(x)} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{n^2(n^2\pi x - 3/2)}{\pi x - 3/2} e^{-(n^2-1)\pi x}$$

converges and is monotone decreasing on $[1, \infty)$. Hence, $F(x)/a_1(x)$ has an upper bound $M = F(1)/a_1(1)$.

In the upper critical strip D the defined infinite integral in (3.1) is finite. In fact,

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{1}{2}\xi(s) \right| &= \left| \int_1^{\infty} F(x) \left(x^{\frac{s}{2}} + x^{\frac{1-s}{2}} \right) dx \right| \\ &\leq \int_1^{\infty} \frac{F(x)}{a_1(x)} a_1(x) \left(\left| x^{\frac{s}{2}} \right| + \left| x^{\frac{1-s}{2}} \right| \right) dx \\ &\leq M \int_1^{\infty} \pi \left(\pi x - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-\pi x} \left(x^{\frac{\sigma}{2}} + x^{\frac{1-\sigma}{2}} \right) dx \\ &\leq 2\pi M \int_1^{\infty} \left(\pi x - \frac{3}{2} \right) x^{\frac{1}{2}} e^{-\pi x} dx \\ &= \frac{2M}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_{\pi}^{\infty} \left(y^{\frac{3}{2}} - \frac{3}{2}y^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) e^{-y} dy < \infty, \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

here the substitution $y = \pi x$ is used. Furthermore, the summation and integration can exchange their order. There is a rough estimation below:

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{1}{2}\xi(s) \right| &= \left| \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_1^{\infty} a_n(x) \left(x^{\frac{s}{2}} + x^{\frac{1-s}{2}} \right) dx \right| \\ &\leq 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_1^{\infty} n^2 \pi \left(n^2 \pi x - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-n^2 \pi x} x^{\frac{1}{2}} dx \\ &= 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2 \pi} \int_0^{\infty} n^2 \pi \left[n^2 \pi (y+1) - \frac{3}{2} \right] e^{-n^2 \pi y} (y+1)^{\frac{1}{2}} dy \\ &= 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2 \pi} \int_0^{\infty} \left(w + n^2 \pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) \left(\frac{w}{n^2 \pi} + 1 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} e^{-w} dw \\ &< 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2 \pi} \left[\int_0^{\infty} w \left(\frac{w}{n^2 \pi} + 1 \right) e^{-w} dw \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \left(n^2\pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{w}{n^2\pi} + 1 \right) e^{-w} dw \Big] \\
& = 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2\pi} \left[\frac{1}{n^2\pi} \Gamma(3) + \Gamma(2) + \left(n^2\pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{n^2\pi} \Gamma(2) + \Gamma(1) \right) \right] \\
& = 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(n^2\pi + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2n^2\pi} \right) e^{-n^2\pi} \\
& < 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (n^2\pi + 1) e^{-n^2\pi} < \infty. \tag{3.5}
\end{aligned}$$

Here the substitutions $x = y + 1$ and $n^2\pi y = w$ are used.

Based on the above analysis, the expression of summation form for $\xi(s)/2$ is accepted and the deduction process can be continued.

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{1}{2}\xi(s) & = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_1^\infty a_n(x) \left(x^{\frac{s}{2}} + x^{\frac{1-s}{2}} \right) dx \\
& = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_1^\infty n^2\pi \left(n^2\pi x - \frac{3}{2} \right) x^{\frac{s}{2}} e^{-n^2\pi x} dx \\
& \quad + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_1^\infty n^2\pi \left(n^2\pi x - \frac{3}{2} \right) x^{\frac{1-s}{2}} e^{-n^2\pi x} dx \\
& = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (n^2\pi)^{-\frac{s}{2}} \int_{n^2\pi}^\infty \left(w - \frac{3}{2} \right) w^{\frac{s}{2}} e^{-w} dw \\
& \quad + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (n^2\pi)^{-\frac{1-s}{2}} \int_{n^2\pi}^\infty \left(w - \frac{3}{2} \right) w^{\frac{1-s}{2}} e^{-w} dw \\
& := \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f_n \left(\frac{s}{2} \right) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f_n \left(\frac{1-s}{2} \right). \tag{3.6}
\end{aligned}$$

Here the substitution $n^2\pi x = w$ is used. For $s \in D$, let z stands for $s/2$ or $(1-s)/2$. In view of the estimations in (3.5), the general term $f_n(z)$ should satisfy

$$|f_n(z)| = \left| (n^2\pi)^{-z} \int_{n^2\pi}^\infty \left(w - \frac{3}{2} \right) w^z e^{-w} dw \right|$$

$$< (n^2\pi + 1)e^{-n^2\pi}, \quad (3.7)$$

whose values are about 0.1790 , 4.7311×10^{-5} , 1.5385×10^{-11} , 7.5823×10^{-21} and 6.1827×10^{-33} for the cases with $n = 1, 2, 3, 4$ and 5 . These implies that for all $s \in D$ the magnitude of general term decreases sharply along with the increasing of n , and the first several terms may give very well estimation.

4. To Estimate the Real and Imaginary Parts of $f_n(s/2)$

The rough estimation on the general term $f_n(z)$ in (3.7) only reflects the decreasing property about n . It lacks the variation characteristics with respect to σ and t . In the upper critical strip the variation of $f_n(s/2)$ and $f_n((1-s)/2)$ about σ on $[0, 1]$ may be very limited, yet that about t on $(0, \infty)$ may be obvious. Here we give some estimations on their real parts and imaginary parts.

Let $z = s/2 = \sigma/2 + it/2$, then

$$\begin{aligned} f_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) &= \int_1^\infty n^2\pi \left(n^2\pi x - \frac{3}{2}\right) e^{-n^2\pi x} x^{s/2} dx \\ &= \int_0^\infty n^2\pi \left(n^2\pi e^y - \frac{3}{2}\right) e^{-n^2\pi e^y} e^{sy/2} e^y dy \\ &= \int_0^\infty n^2\pi \left[w_n(y) - \frac{3}{2}\right] e^{-w_n(y)+(1+\sigma/2)y} \cos\left(\frac{t}{2}y\right) dy \\ &\quad + i \int_0^\infty n^2\pi \left[w_n(y) - \frac{3}{2}\right] e^{-w_n(y)+(1+\sigma/2)y} \sin\left(\frac{t}{2}y\right) dy \\ &:= \int_0^\infty F_n(y) \cos\left(\frac{t}{2}y\right) dy + i \int_0^\infty F_n(y) \sin\left(\frac{t}{2}y\right) dy, \end{aligned} \quad (4.1)$$

here the substitutions $x = e^y$ and $w_n(y) = n^2\pi e^y$ are used. To take σ as a constant, the function $F_n(y)$ has monotonicity. In fact, for a given $n (\geq 1)$,

the derivative of $F_n(y)$ satisfies

$$\begin{aligned}
F'_n(y) &= \left\{ n^2 \pi \left[w_n(y) - \frac{3}{2} \right] e^{-w_n(y) + (1+\sigma/2)y} \right\}' \\
&= -n^2 \pi \left[w_n^2(y) - \frac{7+\sigma}{2} w_n(y) + \frac{3(2+\sigma)}{4} \right] e^{-w_n(y) + (1+\sigma/2)y} \\
&< 0
\end{aligned} \tag{4.2}$$

on condition that

$$w_n(y) = n^2 \pi e^y > \frac{7 + \sigma + \sqrt{\sigma^2 + 2\sigma + 25}}{4}, \tag{4.3}$$

whose value varies from 3 to about 3.3229 along with the increasing of σ in $[0, 1]$. Notice that $y \geq 0$, this request is naturally satisfied for $n \geq 2$. For $n = 1$ it requires

$$0 \leq \sigma < \sigma_0 = \frac{4\pi^2 - 14\pi + 6}{2\pi - 3} \approx 0.4557. \tag{4.4}$$

In case $\sigma \geq \sigma_0$, $F_1(y)$ has a unique maximum point whose location is at

$$y = y^*(\sigma) = \log \left(\frac{7 + \sigma + \sqrt{\sigma^2 + 2\sigma + 25}}{4\pi} \right). \tag{4.5}$$

Particularly, the case $\sigma = 1$ corresponds to the upmost location at about 0.0561 which is very near to the left boundary $y = 0$. For all $\sigma \in [0, 1]$ the increment $F_1(y^*(\sigma)) - F_1(0)$ is very small, since on the exponent $\sigma y/2 \ll n^2 \pi e^y$ for all $y \geq 0$.

In the following we consider the case with $0 \leq \sigma \leq \sigma_0$ (for the particular case $\sigma = \sigma_0$, the unique maximum point of $F_1(y)$ is at the left boundary $y = 0$). Under this case, the monotone decreasing property of $F_n(y)$ is maintained for all $n \geq 1$ (see Figure 5). The real part of $f_n(s/2)$ can be

Figure 5: a: The variations of $F_1(y)$ (bold black) and $|F_1(y) \cos(ty/2)|$ along with y ; b: The variations of $F_1(y)$ (bold black) and $|F_1(y) \sin(ty/2)|$ along with y ; c: The variations of $F_2(y)$ (bold black) and $|F_2(y) \cos(ty/2)|$ along with y ; d: The variations of $F_3(y)$ (bold black) and $|F_3(y) \cos(ty/2)|$ along with y . Here we choose $\sigma = 0.4$ and $t = 80$. The solid blue line and the dashed black line separately stand for the positive and negative parts of the function's value respectively.

rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_0^\infty F_n(y) \cos\left(\frac{t}{2}y\right) dy \\
&= \int_0^{\pi/t} F_n(y) \cos\left(\frac{t}{2}y\right) dy + \sum_{k=0}^\infty \int_{(4k+1)\pi/t}^{(4k+5)\pi/t} F_n(y) \cos\left(\frac{t}{2}y\right) dy \\
&= \int_0^{\pi/t} F_n(y) \cos\left(\frac{t}{2}y\right) dy - \sum_{k=0}^\infty \int_0^{4\pi/t} F_n\left(\bar{y} + \frac{(4k+1)\pi}{t}\right) \sin\left(\frac{t}{2}\bar{y}\right) d\bar{y} \\
&= \int_0^{\pi/t} F_n(y) \cos\left(\frac{t}{2}y\right) dy \\
&\quad - \sum_{k=0}^\infty \int_0^{2\pi/t} \left[F_n\left(\bar{y} + \frac{(4k+1)\pi}{t}\right) - F_n\left(\bar{y} + \frac{(4k+3)\pi}{t}\right) \right] \sin\left(\frac{t}{2}\bar{y}\right) d\bar{y} \\
&= \frac{2}{t} F_n(\hat{y}_0) - \frac{4}{t} \sum_{k=0}^\infty \left[F_n\left(\tilde{y}_k + \frac{(4k+1)\pi}{t}\right) - F_n\left(\tilde{y}_k + \frac{(4k+3)\pi}{t}\right) \right] \\
&:= \frac{2n^2\pi}{t} \left(n^2\pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-n^2\pi} \\
&\quad \cdot \left\{ F_n^*(\hat{y}_0) - 2 \sum_{k=0}^\infty \left[F_n^*\left(\tilde{y}_k + \frac{(4k+1)\pi}{t}\right) - F_n^*\left(\tilde{y}_k + \frac{(4k+3)\pi}{t}\right) \right] \right\} \\
&:= \frac{2n^2\pi}{t} \left(n^2\pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-n^2\pi} R_n, \tag{4.6}
\end{aligned}$$

here $0 < \hat{y}_0 < \pi/t$, $0 < \tilde{y}_k < 2\pi/t$ and the *Mean-Value Theorem of Integrals* is used. In view of the expression for $F_n(y)$ we get

$$F_n^*(y) = \frac{n^2\pi e^y - 3/2}{n^2\pi - 3/2} \exp \left\{ -n^2\pi(e^y - 1) + \left(1 + \frac{\sigma}{2}\right)y \right\}, \tag{4.7}$$

which is still a monotone decreasing function. Hence,

$$-1 < -F_n^*\left(\frac{\pi}{t}\right) < F_n^*(\hat{y}_0) - 2F_n^*\left(\tilde{y}_0 + \frac{\pi}{t}\right) < R_n < F_n^*(\hat{y}_0) < 1.$$

This leads to a fine estimation to the real part of $f_n(s/2)$:

$$\left| \Re[f_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right)] \right| = \left| \int_0^\infty F_n(y) \cos\left(\frac{t}{2}y\right) dy \right| < \frac{2n^2\pi}{t} \left(n^2\pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-n^2\pi}. \tag{4.8}$$

The sign of $\Re[f_n(s/2)]$ is not determined, in all probability, for each given $\sigma \in [0, 1]$, it oscillates about 0 along with the increasing of t .

In view of the distributions in Figure 5(b) we see the imaginary part of $f_n(s/2)$ should be positive. In fact,

$$\begin{aligned}
\Im[f_n(\frac{s}{2})] &= \int_0^\infty F_n(y) \sin(\frac{t}{2}y) dy \\
&= \sum_{k=0}^\infty \int_{4k\pi/t}^{4(k+1)\pi/t} F_n(y) \sin(\frac{t}{2}y) dy \\
&= \sum_{k=0}^\infty \int_{4k\pi/t}^{(4k+2)\pi/t} \left[F_n(y) - F_n(y + \frac{2\pi}{t}) \right] \sin(\frac{t}{2}y) dy \\
&= \sum_{k=0}^\infty \left[F_n(\tilde{y}_k) - F_n(\tilde{y}_k + \frac{2\pi}{t}) \right] \int_{4k\pi/t}^{(4k+2)\pi/t} \sin(\frac{t}{2}y) dy \\
&= \frac{4}{t} \sum_{k=0}^\infty \left[F_n(\tilde{y}_k) - F_n(\tilde{y}_k + \frac{2\pi}{t}) \right] \\
&= \frac{4n^2\pi}{t} \left(n^2\pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-n^2\pi} \sum_{k=0}^\infty \left[F_n^*(\tilde{y}_k) - F_n^*(\tilde{y}_k + \frac{2\pi}{t}) \right] \\
&< \frac{4n^2\pi}{t} \left(n^2\pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-n^2\pi} F_n^*(\tilde{y}_0) \\
&\leq \frac{4n^2\pi}{t} \left(n^2\pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-n^2\pi}. \tag{4.9}
\end{aligned}$$

Though the above estimations are made with respect to $\sigma \in [0, \sigma_0]$, they actually hold on the whole interval $[0, 1]$ for $n \geq 2$, since the monotonicity of $F_n(y)$ is always maintained. Based on this, we get the following results:

Theorem 4.1. *In the upper critical strip $D = \{(\sigma, t) | 0 \leq \sigma \leq 1, 0 < t < \infty\}$, the general terms of the two infinite series defined in (3.6) with $n \geq 2$ satisfies the fine estimations below:*

$$\left| \Re[f_n(\frac{s}{2})] \right|, \left| \Re[f_n(\frac{1-s}{2})] \right| < \frac{2n^2\pi}{t} \left(n^2\pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-n^2\pi},$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0 < \Im[f_n(\frac{s}{2})] &< \frac{4n^2\pi}{t} \left(n^2\pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-n^2\pi}, \\
0 > \Im[f_n(\frac{1-s}{2})] &> -\frac{4n^2\pi}{t} \left(n^2\pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-n^2\pi}.
\end{aligned} \tag{4.10}$$

For the case with $n = 1$ and $\sigma \in (\sigma_0, 1]$, $F_1(y)$ has a unique maximum point at $y = y^*(\sigma)$ [defined in (4.5)] which is near to the left boundary $y = 0$. At this time, $F_1^*[y^*(\sigma)]$ is the peak value of $F_1^*(y)$, and the half-period segment which includes this point dominates. Since for this case $F_1(y)$ increases on $[0, y^*(\sigma)]$ and decreases on $[y^*(\sigma), \infty)$, the signs of $\Re[f_n(s/2)]$ and $\Im[f_n(s/2)]$ are not determined. We can only give out some estimations in a rough way. It follows from (4.6) that for this case the estimation in (4.8) can be modified by multiplying a factor

$$2F_1^*[y^*(\sigma)] \leq 2F_1^*[y^*(1)] = 2F_1^* \left[\log \left(\frac{4 + \sqrt{7}}{2\pi} \right) \right] \approx 2.0152.$$

In addition, the real part and imaginary part of $f_n((1-s)/2)$ are similar to those of $f_n(s/2)$. The results for the case $n = 1$ is summarized as follows:

Theorem 4.2. *For the case with $\sigma \in [0, \sigma_0]$ and $t \in (0, \infty)$ [σ_0 is defined in (4.4)], it holds the estimations:*

$$\begin{aligned}
\left| \Re[f_1(\frac{s}{2})] \right| &< \frac{2\pi}{t} \left(\pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-\pi}, \\
0 < \Im[f_1(\frac{s}{2})] &< \frac{4\pi}{t} \left(\pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-\pi},
\end{aligned}$$

For the case with $\sigma \in [1 - \sigma_0, 1]$ and $t \in (0, \infty)$, it holds the estimations:

$$\begin{aligned}
\left| \Re[f_1(\frac{1-s}{2})] \right| &< \frac{2\pi}{t} \left(\pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-\pi}, \\
0 > \Im[f_1(\frac{1-s}{2})] &> -\frac{4\pi}{t} \left(\pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-\pi}.
\end{aligned}$$

For the other cases with $t \in (0, \infty)$ it holds the estimations:

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \Re[f_1(\frac{s}{2})] \right|, \left| \Im[f_1(\frac{s}{2})] \right| &< \frac{4\pi}{t} F_1^*[y^*(\sigma)] \left(\pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-\pi}, \\ \left| \Re[f_1(\frac{1-s}{2})] \right|, \left| \Im[f_1(\frac{1-s}{2})] \right| &< \frac{4\pi}{t} F_1^*[y^*(\sigma)] \left(\pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-\pi}, \end{aligned}$$

where $y^*(\sigma)$ and $F_1^*(y)$ are defined in (4.5) and (4.7) respectively.

To combine the above two theorems we get a corollary below:

Corollary 4.1. For $t \in (0, \infty)$ it holds the estimations:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 < \Im \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f_n(\frac{s}{2}) \right] &< \frac{4}{t} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 \pi \left(n^2 \pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-n^2 \pi}, \quad \sigma \in [0, \sigma_0], \\ 0 > \Im \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f_n(\frac{1-s}{2}) \right] &> -\frac{4}{t} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 \pi \left(n^2 \pi - \frac{3}{2} \right) e^{-n^2 \pi}, \quad \sigma \in [1 - \sigma_0, 1]. \end{aligned}$$

5. To Generalize the Gamma Function

The expressions in (3.6) are involved in an integral of the form:

$$\Gamma^*(z+1, \alpha) = \int_{\alpha}^{\infty} y^z e^{-y} dy \quad (5.1)$$

with $\alpha > 0$, which is related to the known Gamma function with $\Gamma^*(z+1, 0) = \Gamma(z+1)$, where

$$\Gamma(z+1) = \int_0^{\infty} y^z e^{-y} dy. \quad (5.2)$$

Based on this relation, we call the function defined in (5.1) “the generalized Gamma function”. It is easily calculated that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\alpha}^{\infty} y^z e^{-y} dy &= -y^z e^{-y} \Big|_{\alpha}^{\infty} + z \int_{\alpha}^{\infty} y^{z-1} e^{-y} dy \\ &= \alpha^z e^{-\alpha} + z \int_{\alpha}^{\infty} y^{z-1} e^{-y} dy, \end{aligned}$$

which leads to a deduction formula below:

$$\Gamma^*(z + 1, \alpha) = \alpha^z e^{-\alpha} + z\Gamma^*(z, \alpha). \quad (5.3)$$

Theorem 5.1. *For $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\alpha > 0$, the generalized Gamma function has an explicit expression below:*

$$\Gamma^*(m + 1, \alpha) = m! e^{-\alpha} \sum_{k=0}^m \frac{\alpha^k}{k!}. \quad (5.4)$$

Proof. To execute the deduction formula it results in

$$\begin{aligned} & \Gamma^*(m + 1, \alpha) \\ &= \alpha^m e^{-\alpha} + m\Gamma^*(m, \alpha) \\ &= \alpha^m e^{-\alpha} + m [\alpha^{m-1} e^{-\alpha} + (m-1)\Gamma^*(m-1, \alpha)] \\ & \quad \vdots \\ &= e^{-\alpha} [\alpha^m + m\alpha^{m-1} + m(m-1)\alpha^{m-2} + \cdots + m(m-1)\cdots 2 \cdot \alpha] \\ & \quad + m(m-1)\cdots 1 \cdot \Gamma^*(1, \alpha) \\ &= m! e^{-\alpha} \left[\frac{\alpha^m}{m!} + \frac{\alpha^{m-1}}{(m-1)!} + \cdots + \frac{\alpha}{1!} + 1 \right] \\ &= m! e^{-\alpha} \sum_{k=0}^m \frac{\alpha^k}{k!}. \end{aligned}$$

The proof is finished.

Theorem 5.2. *For $\alpha > 0$ and $z \in \mathbb{C}$ with $\text{Re}(z) > -1$, the generalized Gamma function and the common Gamma function hold the following relation:*

$$\Gamma^*(z + 1, \alpha) = \Gamma(z + 1) \left[1 - e^{-\alpha} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^{z+k}}{\Gamma(z + k + 1)} \right]. \quad (5.5)$$

Proof. To rewrite the integral into a difference of two part we have

$$\begin{aligned}\Gamma^*(z+1, \alpha) &= \int_0^\infty y^z e^{-y} dy - \int_0^\alpha y^z e^{-y} dy \\ &= \Gamma(z+1) - \int_0^\alpha y^z e^{-y} dy.\end{aligned}$$

The late part is a finite integral which can be expanded by executing the scheme of “integration by part” m times ($m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$):

$$\begin{aligned}& \int_0^\alpha y^z e^{-y} dy \\ &= \frac{\alpha^{z+1}}{z+1} e^{-\alpha} + \frac{1}{z+1} \int_0^\alpha y^{z+1} e^{-y} dy \\ &= \frac{\alpha^{z+1}}{z+1} e^{-\alpha} + \frac{\alpha^{z+2}}{(z+1)(z+2)} e^{-\alpha} + \frac{1}{(z+1)(z+2)} \int_0^\alpha y^{z+2} e^{-y} dy \\ & \quad \vdots \\ &= e^{-\alpha} \left[\frac{\alpha^{z+1}}{z+1} + \frac{\alpha^{z+2}}{(z+1)(z+2)} + \cdots + \frac{\alpha^{z+m}}{(z+1)(z+2) \cdots (z+m)} \right] \\ & \quad + \frac{1}{(z+1)(z+2) \cdots (z+m)} \int_0^\alpha y^{z+m} e^{-y} dy.\end{aligned}\tag{5.6}$$

To denote $z = a + bi$ ($a > -1$), then

$$(y^{a+m} e^{-y})' = y^{a+m-1} e^{-y} (a+m-y),$$

which indicates that the function $y^{a+m} e^{-y}$ has a unique extreme point at $y = a + m$. Hence, on the interval $[0, \alpha]$ it is monotone increasing provided that $m \geq \alpha - a$. For given α and a we can always choose a big enough m to satisfy this request. The modulus of the remainder term in (5.6) satisfies the estimation below:

$$\left| \frac{1}{(z+1)(z+2) \cdots (z+m)} \int_0^\alpha y^{z+m} e^{-y} dy \right|$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \frac{1}{|(z+1)(z+2)\cdots(z+m)|} \int_0^\alpha y^{a+m} e^{-y} dy \\
&\leq \frac{1}{|(z+1)(z+2)\cdots(z+m)|} \cdot \alpha^{a+m} e^{-\alpha} \cdot \alpha \rightarrow 0 \quad (5.7)
\end{aligned}$$

as $m \rightarrow \infty$. Hence, the expansion in (5.6) can be continued to infinite and

$$\begin{aligned}
\Gamma^*(z+1, \alpha) &= \Gamma(z+1) - \int_0^\alpha y^z e^{-y} dy \\
&= \Gamma(z+1) - e^{-\alpha} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(z+1)\alpha^{z+k}}{\Gamma(z+k+1)} \\
&= \Gamma(z+1) \left[1 - e^{-\alpha} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^{z+k}}{\Gamma(z+k+1)} \right].
\end{aligned}$$

This is the relation in (5.5). The infinite series here is also absolutely convergent. In fact, for any $z \in \mathbb{C}$ with $\operatorname{Re}(z) > -1$, the general terms a_k and a_{k+1} satisfy

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|a_{k+1}|}{|a_k|} = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{\alpha^{z+k+1} \Gamma(z+k+1)}{\Gamma(z+k+2) \alpha^{z+k}} \right| = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{\alpha}{z+k+1} \right| = 0.$$

The proof is finished.

We note that the formula in Theorem 5.1 can be rewritten as

$$\Gamma^*(m+1, \alpha) = m! e^{-\alpha} \sum_{k=0}^m \frac{\alpha^k}{k!} = m! e^{-\alpha} \left[e^\alpha - \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^{m+k}}{(m+k)!} \right]. \quad (5.8)$$

To substitute m by z and replace $(m+k)! = \Gamma(m+k+1)$ with $\Gamma(z+k+1)$ ($k \geq 0$), then we get the analytic continuation formula in Theorem 5.2. This consistency has verified the reliability of the expression in (5.5).

6. The First Symmetric Formula for $\xi(s)$

Based on the result in Theorem 5.2 (with $n^2\pi = \alpha$), let z stands for $s/2$ or $(1-s)/2$ it follows from (3.6) that

$$f_n(z) = \alpha^{-z} \int_\alpha^\infty \left(w - \frac{3}{2} \right) w^z e^{-w} dw$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \alpha^{-z} \left[\Gamma^*(z+2, \alpha) - \frac{3}{2} \Gamma^*(z+1, \alpha) \right] \\
&= \alpha^{-z} \left\{ \Gamma(z+2) \left[1 - e^{-\alpha} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^{z+k+1}}{\Gamma(z+k+2)} \right] \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \frac{3}{2} \Gamma(z+1) \left[1 - e^{-\alpha} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^{z+k}}{\Gamma(z+k+1)} \right] \right\} \\
&= \alpha^{-z} \left[\Gamma(z+1) \left(z - \frac{1}{2} \right) - e^{-\alpha} \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^{z+k}}{\prod_{j=2}^k (z+j)} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{3}{2} e^{-\alpha} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^{z+k}}{\prod_{j=1}^k (z+j)} \right] \\
&= -\Gamma(z+1) \left(\frac{1}{2} - z \right) \alpha^{-z} \\
&\quad + \frac{3\alpha e^{-\alpha}}{2(z+1)} + \left(\frac{1}{2} - z \right) \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^k e^{-\alpha}}{\prod_{j=1}^k (z+j)}. \tag{6.1}
\end{aligned}$$

Here the relation $\Gamma(z+2) = (z+1)\Gamma(z+1)$ is used. The prod function is defined as

$$\prod_{j=1}^k (z+j) = (z+1)(z+2) \cdots (z+k).$$

We note that the expression in (6.1) only holds for finite α , and in substituting α by $n^2\pi$, a natural thing is to delimit an upper bound for n . In view of this we rewrite the infinite series as

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f_n \left(\frac{s}{2} \right) = \sum_{n=1}^N f_n \left(\frac{s}{2} \right) + \delta_N(s), \tag{6.2}$$

where N is the truncated number, the remainder term satisfies the estimation below:

$$\begin{aligned}
|\delta_N(s)| &< \sum_{n=N+1}^{\infty} (n^2\pi + 1) e^{-n^2\pi} \\
&= O \left\{ [(N+1)^2\pi + 1] e^{-(N+1)^2\pi} \right\}, \tag{6.3}
\end{aligned}$$

here the inequality in (3.7) is used. $O\{\}$ stands for the infinitesimal of the same order. Since the general term of this series decreases sharply about n , for a big enough N the effect from the remainder term $\delta_N(s)$ may become too small to be neglected. In fact, the values of $[(N+1)^2\pi + 1]e^{-(N+1)^2\pi}$ are merely 1.5385×10^{-11} , 7.5823×10^{-21} , 6.1827×10^{-33} and 8.7042×10^{-48} for the cases with $N = 2, 3, 4$ and 5 . This indicates that only if N is not small the request is fulfilled.

To denote

$$C_{N,k} = \sum_{n=1}^N (n^2\pi)^k e^{-n^2\pi} \quad (6.4)$$

and recall that

$$\frac{1}{2}\xi(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f_n\left(\frac{1-s}{2}\right),$$

we get a symmetric formula as follows:

Theorem 6.1. *In the upper critical strip $D = \{(\sigma, t) | 0 \leq \sigma \leq 1, 0 < t < \infty\}$ the function $\xi(s)$ with $s = \sigma + it$ satisfies the first symmetric formula below:*

$$\begin{aligned} \xi(s) = & - \sum_{n=1}^N \Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2} + 1\right)(1-s)(n^2\pi)^{-s/2} + \frac{3C_{N,1}}{s/2 + 1} \\ & + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{C_{N,k}(1-s)}{\prod_{j=1}^k (s/2 + j)} + \delta_N(s) \\ & - \sum_{n=1}^N \Gamma\left(\frac{1-s}{2} + 1\right)s(n^2\pi)^{-(1-s)/2} + \frac{3C_{N,1}}{(3-s)/2} \\ & + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{C_{N,k}s}{\prod_{j=1}^k [(1-s)/2 + j]} + \delta_N(1-s). \end{aligned} \quad (6.5)$$

We note that, though the first term of this symmetric formula can be seen as a finite approximation to the original definition

$$\xi(s) = (s-1)\pi^{-s/2}\Gamma(s/2+1)\sum_{n=1}^{\infty}n^{-s},$$

the reformed formula is still valuable. There are two reasons for this. Firstly, the symmetric property $\xi(1-s) = \xi(s)$ in the original definition is implicit. Yet in the symmetric formula this property is distinctly reflected. The two parts in (6.5) [each part includes 4 terms in form] exchange into each other in case s is replaced with $1-s$. Particularly, the important result $\Im[\xi(1/2+it)] \equiv 0$ is maintained by the symmetric formula. It can be easily checked by applying the Reflection Principle. Secondly, in the original definition the infinite series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty}n^{-s}$ does not converge in D . The function $\xi(s)$ should be understood in a sense of analytical-continuation in (1.4) which is involved in a very complex infinite integral. The symmetric formula has eliminated this integral. It is countable. Particularly, it follows from (6.3) that the sums from $N+1$ to ∞ can be neglected only if N is not small. It reflects the advantage of the reformation.

To calculate $\xi(s)$ we rewrite the expression in (6.5) as

$$\begin{aligned}\xi(s) &= -\phi_N(s) + \psi_{N,\infty}(s) + \delta_N(s) \\ &\quad -\phi_N(1-s) + \psi_{N,\infty}(1-s) + \delta_N(1-s),\end{aligned}\tag{6.6}$$

in which

$$\begin{aligned}\phi_N(s) &= \sum_{n=1}^N \Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2}+1\right)(1-s)(n^2\pi)^{-s/2}, \\ \psi_{N,\infty}(s) &= \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \psi_{N,K}(s)\end{aligned}$$

$$= \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \left[\frac{3C_{N,1}}{s/2 + 1} + \sum_{k=2}^K \frac{C_{N,k}(1-s)}{\prod_{j=1}^k (s/2 + j)} \right], \quad (6.7)$$

here $\psi_{N,K}(s)$ means firstly taking the sum from 1 to N with respect to n and then taking the sum from 1 to K with respect to k .

7. To Approximate the First Symmetric Formula of $\xi(s)$

Firstly, we take the conversion:

$$\begin{aligned} & \Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2} + 1\right)(1-s)(n^2\pi)^{-s/2} \\ &= \exp \left\{ \log \Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2} + 1\right) + \log(1-s) - \frac{s}{2} \log(n^2\pi) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (7.1)$$

By using the Euler-Maclaurin summation formula, for an arbitrary z with $\Re(z) > -1$, the function $\log \Gamma(z + 1)$ can be effectively estimated. The known result named *Stirling's series* [see page 109 in [3], $\Pi(z) = \Gamma(z + 1)$] is as follows:

$$\log \Gamma(z + 1) = \left(z + \frac{1}{2}\right) \log z - z + \frac{1}{2} \log 2\pi + \epsilon(z) \quad (7.2)$$

with

$$\epsilon(z) = \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{B_{2j}}{2j(2j-1)z^{2j-1}} - \int_0^\infty \frac{\overline{B}_{2m}(x)}{2m(z+x)^{2m}} dx, \quad (7.3)$$

in which $\overline{B}_{2m}(x) = B_{2m}(x - [x])$ is the $2m$ -th order Bernoulli polynomial ($[x]$ is the integer part of x). $B_{2j} = B_{2j}(0)$ with $1 \leq j \leq m$ are the Bernoulli numbers whose values are:

$$B_2 = \frac{1}{6}, \quad B_4 = -\frac{1}{30}, \quad B_6 = \frac{1}{42}, \quad B_8 = -\frac{1}{30}, \quad B_{10} = \frac{5}{66}, \dots$$

We note that the increasing of t is favorable for the estimation of $\epsilon(s/2)$. In case $t \gg \sigma$ the first several terms of the series may give a good estimation. For $(\sigma, t) \in D$, there is

$$\begin{aligned}
& \log \Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2} + 1\right) + \log(1 - s) - \frac{s}{2} \log(n^2 \pi) \\
&= \frac{1 + \sigma + it}{2} \log \frac{\sigma + it}{2} - \frac{\sigma + it}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \log 2\pi + \epsilon\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \\
& \quad + \log(1 - \sigma - it) - \frac{\sigma + it}{2} \log(n^2 \pi) \\
&= \frac{1 + \sigma + it}{2} \left[\log \frac{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + t^2}}{2} + i \arctan\left(\frac{t}{\sigma}\right) \right] \\
& \quad - \frac{\sigma + it}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \log 2\pi + \epsilon\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) + \log \sqrt{(1 - \sigma)^2 + t^2} \\
& \quad - i \arctan\left(\frac{t}{1 - \sigma}\right) - \frac{\sigma + it}{2} \log(n^2 \pi) \\
&:= h_n(\sigma, t) + i\theta_n(\sigma, t). \tag{7.4}
\end{aligned}$$

For all $t > 0$ we always accept the settings

$$\arctan\left(\frac{t}{\sigma}\right) \equiv \pi/2, \quad \arctan\left(\frac{t}{1 - \sigma}\right) \equiv \pi/2$$

for $\sigma = 0$ and $\sigma = 1$ respectively. Specifically, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
h_n(\sigma, t) &= \frac{1 + \sigma}{2} \log \frac{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + t^2}}{2} - \frac{\pi t}{4} + \frac{t}{2} \arctan\left(\frac{\sigma}{t}\right) + \frac{1}{2} \log 2\pi \\
& \quad + \log \sqrt{(1 - \sigma)^2 + t^2} - \frac{\sigma}{2} \log(n^2 \pi e) + \Re[\epsilon\left(\frac{s}{2}\right)]. \\
\theta_n(\sigma, t) &= \frac{t}{2} \log \frac{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + t^2}}{2n^2 \pi e} - \frac{(1 - \sigma)\pi}{4} - \frac{1 + \sigma}{2} \arctan\left(\frac{\sigma}{t}\right) \\
& \quad + \arctan\left(\frac{1 - \sigma}{t}\right) + \Im[\epsilon\left(\frac{s}{2}\right)]. \tag{7.5}
\end{aligned}$$

Here the remainder term is defined as:

$$\epsilon\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) = \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{B_{2j}}{2j(2j-1)(s/2)^{2j-1}} - \int_0^\infty \frac{\overline{B}_{2m}(x)}{2m(s/2+x)^{2m}} dx. \tag{7.6}$$

In addition, it follows from the reflection principle that $h_n(\sigma, -t) = h_n(\sigma, t)$ and $\theta_n(\sigma, -t) = -\theta_n(\sigma, t)$.

To denote $A_n(\sigma, t) = e^{h_n(\sigma, t)}$ and return to the relation in (7.1) we get

$$\begin{aligned}\phi_N(s) &= \sum_{n=1}^N A_n(\sigma, t) e^{i\theta_n(\sigma, t)} \\ \phi_N(1-s) &= \sum_{n=1}^N A_n(1-\sigma, t) e^{-i\theta_n(1-\sigma, t)}.\end{aligned}\tag{7.7}$$

Besides the infinite series about n , the infinite series about k in the symmetric formula needs to be approximated. For this aim, we make the truncation

$$\psi_{N,\infty}(s) = \psi_{N,K}(s) + \delta_{N,K}^*(s),\tag{7.8}$$

here K is an integer which is large enough. In the following we estimate the remainder $\delta_{N,K}^*(s)$.

Before making the error estimation, we firstly consider the product $(z+1)(z+2)\cdots(z+K)$ under the settings $z > -1$. It follows from the Euler-Maclaurin summation formula (see page 104 in [3]) that

$$\begin{aligned}\sum_{k=1}^K \log(z+k) &= \int_1^K \log(z+x) dx + \frac{1}{2}[\log(z+1) + \log(z+K)] + \epsilon_4(z) \\ &= (z+K + \frac{1}{2}) \log(z+K) - (z + \frac{1}{2}) \log(z+1) \\ &\quad -K + 1 + \epsilon_4(z)\end{aligned}\tag{7.9}$$

in which

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_4(z) &= -\frac{1}{12} \left[\frac{1}{z+1} - \frac{1}{z+K} \right] + \frac{1}{360} \left[\frac{1}{(z+1)^3} - \frac{1}{(z+K)^3} \right] \\ &\quad + \int_1^K \frac{\overline{B}_4(x)}{4(z+x)^4} dx.\end{aligned}\tag{7.10}$$

To make analytic continuation we see it holds for all $z = a + bi$ with $a > -1$.

Its real part reads

$$h_K^*(a, b) = K \log \frac{r_K}{e} + \left(a + \frac{1}{2}\right) \log \frac{r_K}{r_1} + 1 + b(\theta_1 - \theta_K) + \Re[\epsilon_4(z)], \quad (7.11)$$

in which

$$\begin{aligned} r_1 &= \sqrt{(a+1)^2 + b^2}, & r_K &= \sqrt{(a+K)^2 + b^2}, \\ \theta_1 &= \arctan\left(\frac{b}{a+1}\right), & \theta_K &= \arctan\left(\frac{b}{a+K}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (7.12)$$

We note that the relation $h_K^*(a, -b) = h_K^*(a, b)$ holds [the modulus of $(z+1)(z+2)\cdots(z+K)$ remains unchanged in case $z = a + bi$ is substituted by $z = a - bi$].

For fixed N and $a \geq 0$, there always a large enough K such that $K > N^2\pi$. Under this settings, the function $y^{a+K}e^{-y}$ increases on $[0, n^2\pi]$ for all $1 \leq n \leq N$, the function $y^{K+1}e^{-y}$ also increases on $[0, K+1]$. It follows from (5.6) and (6.7) that ($z = s/2$):

$$\begin{aligned} |\delta_{N,K}^*(s)| &= \left| \sum_{k=K+1}^{\infty} \frac{C_{N,k}(1-2z)}{\prod_{j=1}^k (z+j)} \right| \\ &= \frac{|1-2z|}{|\prod_{j=1}^K (z+j)|} \left| \sum_{n=1}^N (n^2\pi)^{-z} \int_0^{n^2\pi} y^{z+K} e^{-y} dy \right| \\ &< \frac{|1-2z|}{|\prod_{j=1}^K (z+j)|} \sum_{n=1}^N (n^2\pi)^{-a} (n^2\pi)^{a+K+1} e^{-n^2\pi} \\ &< \frac{|1-2z| N(N^2\pi)^{K+1} e^{-N^2\pi}}{|\prod_{j=1}^K (z+j)|} \\ &< \bar{r}_0 \left[\frac{\sqrt{2}eN^2\pi}{a+b+K} \right]^K \left[\frac{r_1}{r_K} \right]^{a+1/2} e^{-N^2\pi + \log(N^3\pi) - 1 - b(\theta_1 - \theta_K) - \Re[\epsilon_4(z)]}, \end{aligned} \quad (7.13)$$

in which $\bar{r}_0 = \sqrt{(1-2a)^2 + b^2}$. Here the inequality $(a+K)^2 + b^2 \geq (a+K+b)^2/2$ is used. Particularly, for the case with $b+K > \sqrt{2e\pi}N^2 \approx 12.0770N^2$ the magnitude of the remainder term decreases very quick along with the increasing of K and $b = t/2$.

To denote the real and imaginary parts of $\psi_{N,K}(s)$ by $P_{N,K}$ and $Q_{N,K}$ respectively, we check their magnitudes by numerical approach. For example, for the case with $\sigma = 1/2$, $t = 4\pi$, $N = 4$ and $K = 100$ ($b+K \approx 106.2832 < \sqrt{2e\pi}N^2 \approx 193.2321$), $P_{N,K}$, $Q_{N,K}$ and $|\delta_{N,K}^*(s)|$ have the approximate values bellow:

$$P_{4,100} = -0.0017, \quad Q_{4,100} = 0.0855, \quad |\delta_{4,100}^*| \leq 2.6545 \times 10^{-11},$$

here the exact complex version of upper-bound formula (the first inequality) for $|\delta_{N,K}^*(s)|$ in (7.13) is used. For the case with $K = 200$ ($b+K \approx 206.2832 > \sqrt{2e\pi}N^2 \approx 193.2321$) we get $|\delta_{4,200}^*| \leq 3.2124 \times 10^{-58}$. To substitute $t = 4\pi$ by $t = 40$ the values become

$$P_{4,100} = 8.7411 \times 10^{-14}, \quad Q_{4,100} = 0.0226, \quad |\delta_{4,100}^*| \leq 5.2281 \times 10^{-19}.$$

In addition, $|\delta_{4,200}^*| \leq 2.6243 \times 10^{-66}$.

These calculations have verified the result: The magnitude of $\delta_{N,K}^*(s)$ decreases very rapid along with the increasing of K and t . It is much smaller than that of $\psi_{N,K}(s)$ and can be safely neglected provided that K is large enough. The first several hundreds terms are enough for approximating the infinite series about k .

To combine the relations in (7.7) and (7.8), for suitably chosen N and K the first symmetric formula in (6.5) can be rewritten.

Theorem 7.1. *In the upper critical strip $D = \{(\sigma, t) | 0 \leq \sigma \leq 1, 0 < t < \infty\}$ the function $\xi(s)$ satisfies the finite approximation formula below:*

$$\begin{aligned}
\xi(s) = & - \sum_{n=1}^N A_n(\sigma, t) e^{i\theta_n(\sigma, t)} + \frac{3C_{N,1}}{s/2 + 1} \\
& + \sum_{k=2}^K \frac{C_{N,k}(1-s)}{\prod_{j=1}^k (s/2 + j)} + \delta_N(s) + \delta_{N,K}^*(s) \\
& - \sum_{n=1}^N A_n(1-\sigma, t) e^{-i\theta_n(1-\sigma, t)} + \frac{3C_{N,1}}{(3-s)/2} \\
& + \sum_{k=2}^K \frac{C_{N,k}s}{\prod_{j=1}^k [(1-s)/2 + j]} + \delta_N(1-s) + \delta_{N,K}^*(1-s) \quad (7.14)
\end{aligned}$$

with $s = \sigma + it$ and $K > \sqrt{2}e\pi N^2 - 4\pi$, where $\delta_N(s)$ and $\delta_{N,K}^*(s)$ satisfy the estimations in (6.3) and (7.13), respectively.

This formula accords with our knowledge already known, such as the listed results in *Section 1&2*. Particularly, in the series $\sum_{n=1}^N$ the first mode dominates [the amplitude $A_1(\sigma, t)$ has the maximum magnitude], and for the case with $\sigma = 1/2$ and $t \gg 1$ the corresponding frequency:

$$\begin{aligned}
\theta_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, t\right) &= \frac{t}{2} \log \frac{\sqrt{t^2 + 1/4}}{2\pi e} - \frac{\pi}{8} + \frac{1}{4} \arctan \frac{1}{2t} + \dots \\
&\approx \frac{t}{2} \log \frac{t}{2\pi e} - \frac{\pi}{8}.
\end{aligned}$$

is in perfect agreement with the known dominating frequency. As for the optimal phase angle $\alpha = 4\pi/3$ fitted out in *Section 2*, one can check it with the above approximation formula by numerical-simulation approach. In addition, to estimate the zero points on the critical line, here the complex contour integral in Riemann-Siegel formula is avoided, and it only needs to calculate finite terms of the uniformly-convergent sums.

8. The Second Symmetric Formulas for $\xi(s)$

In view of the estimation in (7.13), to do the expansion the condition $|b| + K > \sqrt{2}e\pi N^2 \approx 12.0770N^2$ is enough. To get a uniform limit about n and k we choose $K = 13N^2$. Notice that the remainders $\delta_N(s)$, $\delta_{N,13N^2}^*(s)$, $\delta_N(1-s)$, $\delta_{N,13N^2}^*(s) \rightarrow 0$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$, the convergence properties of the series are ensured and the formula in (6.6) can be reformed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\xi(s) &= \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{n=1}^N 2f_n\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) + \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{n=1}^N 2f_n\left(\frac{1-s}{2}\right), \\
&= -\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \phi_N(s) + \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \psi_{N,13N^2}(s) \\
&\quad - \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \phi_N(1-s) + \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \psi_{N,13N^2}(1-s) \\
&= \xi(s) + \psi_{\infty,\infty}(s) + \xi(1-s) + \psi_{\infty,\infty}(1-s), \tag{8.1}
\end{aligned}$$

here the original definition $\xi(s) = \Gamma(s/2+1)(s-1) \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (n^2\pi)^{-s/2}$ is recalled. $\psi_{N,13N^2}(s)$ means firstly taking the sum from 1 to $13N^2$ with respect to k and then taking the sum from 1 to N with respect to n . Based on this we get $-\xi(1-s) = \psi_{\infty,\infty}(s) + \psi_{\infty,\infty}(1-s)$. To substitute s by $1-s$ it becomes $-\xi(s) = \psi_{\infty,\infty}(1-s) + \psi_{\infty,\infty}(s)$.

Besides the upper critical strip D , the above deductions also hold for the lower one $D' = \{(\sigma, t) | 0 \leq \sigma \leq 1, -\infty < t < 0\}$, it only needs to substitute s by \bar{s} . However, the case $t = 0$ can not be included in, since at this time $\xi(s)$ is real and $(1, 0)$ is its singular point. With new denotations

$$C_k = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (n^2\pi)^k e^{-n^2\pi}, \tag{8.2}$$

we get another symmetric formula:

Theorem 8.1. *In the domain $\Omega = \{(\sigma, t) | 0 \leq \sigma \leq 1, t \neq 0\}$ the function $\xi(s)$ satisfies the second symmetric formula below:*

$$\begin{aligned}
-\xi(s) &= \frac{3C_1}{s/2 + 1} + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{C_k(1-s)}{\prod_{j=1}^k (s/2 + j)} \\
&+ \frac{3C_1}{(1-s)/2 + 1} + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{C_k s}{\prod_{j=1}^k [(1-s)/2 + j]} \quad (8.3)
\end{aligned}$$

with $s = \sigma + it$.

Relative to the first symmetric formula, this one is more accurate and concise, and the most attractive factor is that for $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, the coefficients C_k are related to the derivatives of the known function $\varphi(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2\pi x}$ at $x = 1$. These characteristics are more suitable for theoretical demonstration.

By the way, to make an estimation on the coefficient C_k is helpful. For fixed k , the general term $c_{n,k} = (n^2\pi)^k e^{-n^2\pi}$ decreases sharply along with the increasing of n when $n^2\pi > k$, so the infinite series converges and C_k is finite. Furthermore, since the continuous function $x^k e^{-x}$ obtains its maximum value at $x = k$, the increasing of C_k along k has an oscillating manner, and in case $n^2\pi \approx k$ it attains its maximum value in the relative sense. For $n_0 = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$, there exist $k_0 = 3, 13, 28, 50, 79, \dots$ accordingly such that $n_0^2\pi - 1/2 < k_0 < n_0^2\pi + 1/2$, and for these cases $C_{k_0} > c_{n_0, k_0} = (n_0^2\pi)^{k_0} e^{-n_0^2\pi} \approx k_0^{k_0} e^{-k_0}$. Except c_{n_0, k_0} , the largest two terms for C_k are c_{n_0-1, k_0} and c_{n_0+1, k_0} . Correspondingly, the relative ratios reads:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{c_{n_0-1, k_0}}{c_{n_0, k_0}} &= \left(1 - \frac{1}{n_0}\right)^{2k_0} e^{(2n_0-1)\pi} \approx \left(1 - \frac{1}{n_0}\right)^{2n_0^2\pi} e^{(2n_0-1)\pi}, \\
\frac{c_{n_0+1, k_0}}{c_{n_0, k_0}} &= \left(1 + \frac{1}{n_0}\right)^{2k_0} e^{-(2n_0+1)\pi} \approx \left(1 + \frac{1}{n_0}\right)^{2n_0^2\pi} e^{-(2n_0+1)\pi}.
\end{aligned}$$

Notice that

$$\begin{aligned} 2n_0^2\pi \log\left(1 - \frac{1}{n_0}\right) + (2n_0 - 1)\pi &= -2\pi - \sum_{k=3}^{\infty} \frac{2\pi}{kn_0^{k-1}}, \\ 2n_0^2\pi \log\left(1 + \frac{1}{n_0}\right) - (2n_0 + 1)\pi &= -2\pi + \sum_{k=3}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k-1}2\pi}{kn_0^{k-1}}, \end{aligned}$$

we see $c_{n_0-1,k_0}/c_{n_0,k_0}$ and $c_{n_0+1,k_0}/c_{n_0,k_0}$ separately increases and decreases to $e^{-2\pi} \approx 0.0019$ as $n_0 \rightarrow \infty$. Hence, for the case with $k_0 \approx n_0^2\pi$, c_{n_0,k_0} is the dominating term, and from the numerical calculation we see it possesses more than 99% value of C_{k_0} . Certainly, for the other cases with $k \neq k_0$ the terms are away from the maximum extreme point of $x^k e^{-k}$ and the values of C_k become relative smaller. According to the estimation in (7.9), the magnitude of the dominate term $k_0^{k_0} e^{-k_0}$ approximates that of $\Gamma(k_0 + 1/2) \approx (k_0 - 1/2)^{k_0} e^{1-k_0}$. Roughly, for every given k the magnitude of the sum is not bigger than that of $\Gamma(k + 1/2)$. A fine estimation is given in the following.

Let $f_k(x) = (x^2\pi)^k e^{-x^2\pi}$, it follows from the Euler-Maclaurin summation formula (see page 99 in [3]) that

$$\begin{aligned} C_k &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (n^2\pi)^k e^{-n^2\pi} = \int_1^{\infty} (x^2\pi)^k e^{-x^2\pi} dx + \frac{1}{2} [f_k(1) + f_k(\infty)] + R_{1,k} \\ &= \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \int_{\pi}^{\infty} y^{k-1/2} e^{-y} dy + \frac{1}{2}\pi^k e^{-\pi} + R_{1,k} \\ &= \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \Gamma\left(k + \frac{1}{2}\right) (1 - \beta_k) + \frac{1}{2}\pi^k e^{-\pi} + R_{1,k}, \end{aligned} \tag{8.4}$$

in which

$$R_{1,k} = \int_1^{\infty} \left(x - [x] - \frac{1}{2}\right) f'_k(x) dx, \quad \beta_k = e^{-\pi} \sum_{p=k+1}^{\infty} \frac{\pi^{p-1/2}}{\Gamma(p+1/2)}$$

with $0 < \beta_k < 1$. Here the formula for generalized Gamma function in

Theorem 5.2 is used. We note that the remainder $R_{1,k}$ here is not necessarily small.

To synthesize the above analysis we see, for a big enough k , there is a bounded constant $L(> 0)$ such that

$$C_k \leq \frac{L}{2\sqrt{\pi}}\Gamma(k + \frac{1}{2}). \quad (8.5)$$

With this estimation, a natural thing is to check the necessary condition for the convergence of the series. In fact, to denote $z = s/2 = a + bi$, then for $k \geq 2$, $0 \leq a \leq 1/2$ and $b \neq 0$ we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{C_k(1-2z)}{\prod_{j=1}^k (s/2 + j)} \right| \leq \frac{L\Gamma(k + 1/2)|1-2z|}{2\sqrt{\pi}|\prod_{j=1}^k (z + j)|} \\ & = \frac{L}{2}\sqrt{(1-2a)^2 + b^2} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^k \frac{j-1/2}{\sqrt{(a+j)^2 + b^2}} \rightarrow 0 \end{aligned} \quad (8.6)$$

as $k \rightarrow \infty$. The convergence property of the series needs no verification since the remainders tend to 0 which have already proved.

9. The Third Symmetric Formulas for $\xi(s)$

To denote $z = s/2$, notice that for $k \geq 2$

$$\frac{C_k(1/2 - z)}{\prod_{j=1}^k (z + j)} = \frac{C_k(1/2 + k)}{\prod_{j=1}^k (z + j)} - \frac{C_k}{\prod_{j=1}^{k-1} (z + j)}, \quad (9.1)$$

the formula in (8.3) can be rewritten and we get another result.

Theorem 9.1. *In the domain $\Omega = \{(\sigma, t) | 0 \leq \sigma \leq 1, t \neq 0\}$ the function $\xi(s)$ satisfies the third symmetric formula below:*

$$-\xi(s) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{2a_k}{\prod_{j=1}^k (s/2 + j)} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{2a_k}{\prod_{j=1}^k [(1-s)/2 + j]} \quad (9.2)$$

with $s = \sigma + it$ and $a_k = (1/2 + k)C_k - C_{k+1}$.

For application, this formula is more convenient than the one in (8.3), since the variable s in the numerator vanishes. To denote

$$\psi_{\infty,K}^*(s) = \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{2a_k}{\prod_{j=1}^k (s/2 + j)}, \quad (9.3)$$

then we get

$$\psi_{\infty,K}^*(s) = \psi_{\infty,K}(s) - \frac{2C_{K+1}}{\prod_{j=1}^K (s/2 + j)}. \quad (9.4)$$

As the partial-sum sequence concerned, to add the additional term may be helpful.

By the way, the third symmetric formula can be also deduced by the direct-expansion approach. It follows from (3.1) and (3.2) that

$$\frac{1}{2}\xi(s) = \int_1^{\infty} f'(x)[x^{s/2} + x^{(1-s)/2}] dx \quad (9.5)$$

with $f(x) = \varphi(x)/2 + x\varphi'(x)$ and $\varphi(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2\pi x}$.

Let z stands for $s/2$ or $(1-s)/2$, to make the expansion as in (5.6) we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_1^{\infty} f'(x)x^z dx \\ &= -\frac{f'(1)}{z+1} - \frac{1}{z+1} \int_1^{\infty} f''(x)x^{z+1} dx \\ &= \frac{(-1)^1 f'(1)}{z+1} + \frac{(-1)^2 f''(1)}{(z+1)(z+2)} + \frac{(-1)^2}{(z+1)(z+2)} \int_1^{\infty} f'''(x)x^{z+2} dx \\ & \quad \vdots \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{(-1)^k f^{(k)}(1)}{\prod_{j=1}^k (z+j)} + R_K(z), \end{aligned} \quad (9.6)$$

where $(-1)^k f^{(k)}(1) = a_k$ with $f^{(k)}(x) = (k+1/2)\varphi^{(k)}(x) + x\varphi^{(k+1)}(x)$ and

$$R_K(z) = \frac{(-1)^K}{\prod_{j=1}^K (z+j)} \int_1^{\infty} f^{(K+1)}(x)x^{K+z} dx. \quad (9.7)$$

The difficulty of this approach lies in proving $|R_K(z)| \rightarrow 0$ as $K \rightarrow \infty$. A feasible improvement measure is to make the decomposition:

$$\int_1^\infty f'(x)x^z dx = \int_0^\infty f'(x)x^z dx - \int_0^1 f'(x)x^z dx$$

and expand the second part.

10. To Check the Zero Points on the Critical Line $\sigma = 1/2$

Notice that in the upper critical strip the nearest several zero points on the critical line $\sigma = 1/2$ are already found by numerical approach (see *Section 1&2*), we borrow them to verify the validity of the deduced 3 symmetric formulas.

On the critical line the imaginary part of $\xi(s)$ vanishes, and for this case the expressions in (7.14), (8.3) and (9.2) are simplified as:

$$\begin{aligned}\xi(s) &= -2\Re\phi_N(s) + 2\Re\psi_{N,K}(s) + 2\Re[\delta_N(s) + \delta_{N,K}^*(s)], \\ \xi(s) &= -2\Re\psi_{\infty,K}(s), \\ \xi(s) &= -2\Re\psi_{\infty,K}^*(s)\end{aligned}\tag{10.1}$$

with $s = 1/2 + it$. Here $\sum_{n=1}^N A_n(1/2, t) \cos \theta_n(1/2, t)$ is substituted by the original complex form $\Re\phi_N(s)$ which is more convenient for simulation. Only if N and K are suitably chosen, the remainder terms may become too small to be neglected. For this case, the zero points on the critical line $\sigma = 1/2$ can be separately approximated by the discrete solutions of the equations:

$$\begin{aligned}U_1(1/2, t) &= -2\Re\phi_N(s) + 2\Re\psi_{N,K}(s) = 0, \\ U_2(1/2, t) &= -2\Re\psi_{N,K}(s) = 0, \\ U_3(1/2, t) &= -2\Re\psi_{N,K}^*(s) = 0\end{aligned}\tag{10.2}$$

with respect to $t \in [4\pi, \infty)$. Notice that $\sigma \ll t$, we truncate the remainder term $\epsilon(s/2)$ to the 4-th order, that is $m = 2$. For this case, the approximation formula is

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_N(s) = \sum_{n=1}^N \exp \left\{ \frac{1+s}{2} \log \frac{s}{2} - \frac{s}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \log 2\pi + \log(1-s) \right. \\ \left. + \frac{1}{6s} - \frac{1}{45s^3} - \frac{s}{2} \log(n^2\pi) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (10.3)$$

For the first formula in (10.2), the estimation in (6.3) indicates that a small N is enough for the finite approximation. In fact, the upper bound of $|\delta_N(s)|$ of $N = 5$ is lower than that of $N = 4$ at about 15 orders. This is a wide difference! The first 4 terms approximate the infinite series about n very well, and the error is too small to be neglected. In view of this we choose $N = 4$ for all the calculations below. As for the series about k , it follows from the calculation results in *Section 8* that $K = 200$ is enough. For this case the inequality $K > \sqrt{2}e\pi N^2 - 4\pi \approx 180.6658$ holds. For the second and the third formulas in (10.2), we choose $K = 300$, and C_k is approximated by $\sum_{n=1}^{5000} (n^2\pi)^k e^{-n^2\pi}$, that is, $N = 5000$ is chosen.

It follows from the calculation results in *Figure 6* that, in case the step for t is chosen as $dt = 0.01$, the locations of the first 10 zero points given by $U_1(1/2, t)$ are at about

$$\begin{aligned} 1/2 + 14.13i, & \quad 1/2 + 21.02i, \\ 1/2 + 25.01i, & \quad 1/2 + 30.42i, \\ 1/2 + 32.94i, & \quad 1/2 + 37.59i, \\ 1/2 + 40.92i, & \quad 1/2 + 43.33i, \\ 1/2 + 48.00i, & \quad 1/2 + 49.77i. \end{aligned} \quad (10.4)$$

To compare with the known ones listed in (1.8) we see the absolute error is less than 0.01. So the first formula is valid. Those given by $U_2(1/2, t)$ are near to the listed zeros, and the second formula is basically reasonable, nothing but the error is slightly larger (the largest error is about 0.6). The curve of $U_3(1/2, t)$ almost coincides with that of $U_1(1/2, t)$, and the output zero points also near to the ones in (1.8) with error less than 0.01. This indicates that the third formula is also valid.

Figure 6: The variations of $U_1(1/2, t)$, $U_2(1/2, t)$ and $U_3(1/2, t)$ along with the increasing of t in $[13, 51]$ with step $dt = 0.01$. a: The actually plots. b: The magnified plots with a multiplier $e^{0.7t}$. The 3 formulas in (10.2) with $N = 4$ & $K = 200$, $N = 5000$ & $K = 300$ and $N = 5000$ & $K = 300$ are separately adopted.

In case the step for t is chosen as $dt = 0.000, 000, 1$, the first 6 zero points

given by $U_1(1/2, t)$ are at about

$$\begin{aligned} &1/2 + 14.1347251i, & 1/2 + 21.0220396i, \\ &1/2 + 25.0108575i, & 1/2 + 30.4248761i, \\ &1/2 + 32.9350615i, & 1/2 + 37.5861781i, \end{aligned}$$

They are exactly same to those in (1.8). From the 7-th one the random calculation error appears (under Matlab platform). When the step is chosen as $dt = 0.000, 1$, the absolute error of 10^{-4} for the 7-th to the 10-th zero points can be ensured.

In summary, the first 10 zero points on the critical line $\sigma = 1/2$ have been recognized with very high accuracy by $U_1(1/2, t)$, and this has verified the validity of the finite approximation formula in (7.14). $N = 4$ and $K = 200$ are enough for the calculation. Fundamentally speaking, this has embodied the advantage of the first symmetric formula in (6.5). The third symmetric formula in (9.2) may give almost the same high-accuracy results, only if N and K are large enough. Here $N = 5000$ and $K = 300$ are chosen. As numerical simulation concerned, the first formula is relatively superior (with small N and K). As theoretical deduction concerned, the third formula is relatively superior [without estimation on $\Gamma(s/2 + 1)$]. The second formula in (8.3) has large simulation error and it is not recommended. In view of these, we make further simulation with the first formula.

The application of finite approximation formula in (7.14) can be extended. To get a direct understanding on the change characteristics of $\xi(s)$, we add the variation of σ on $[0, 1]$ and make 3-dimensional numerical simulations for

its real and imaginary parts by

$$\begin{aligned} U(\sigma, t) &= \Re[-\phi_N(s) + \psi_{N,K}(s) - \phi_N(1-s) + \psi_{N,K}(1-s)], \\ V(\sigma, t) &= \Im[-\phi_N(s) + \psi_{N,K}(s) - \phi_N(1-s) + \psi_{N,K}(1-s)]. \end{aligned} \quad (10.5)$$

From *Figure 6* we see $U(\sigma, t)$ decreases very rapid along with the increasing of t . To show it clearly we also multiply U and V by the factor $e^{0.7t}$.

Figure 7: The variation of $U(\sigma, t)e^{0.7t}$ with respect to $\sigma \in [0, 1]$ and $t \in [13, 51]$. The formula in (10.5) with $N = 4$ and $K = 200$ is adopted.

Figure 7 & 8 show that: (1) the curved surfaces for U and V oscillate about the horizontal surface $z \equiv 0$ with respect to the variable t ; (2) the curves for U and V are separately symmetric and anti-symmetric with respect to the variable σ ; (3) the change of U about σ is very small, yet that of V is big; (4) the σ -oriented zero lines for U and V (with $U = 0$ and $V = 0$) almost maintain straight.

Figure 8: The variation of $V(\sigma, t)e^{0.7t}$ with respect to $\sigma \in [0, 1]$ and $t \in [13, 51]$. The formula in (10.5) with $N = 4$ and $K = 200$ is adopted.

Figure 9 show that the locations of the zero points for U along $\sigma = 1/4$ are very near to those along $\sigma = 1/2$, and they do not coincide with the zero points of V .

11. Equivalent Proposition for the Riemann Hypothesis

The third symmetric formula in (9.2) can be rewritten as:

$$\xi(s) = - \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} [\psi_{\infty, K}^*(s) + \psi_{\infty, K}^*(1-s)] := \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \xi_K(s). \quad (11.1)$$

That is to say, the value of $\xi(s)$ can be approximated by a partial-sum $\xi_K(s)$ in case K is large enough.

For simplicity of deduction we rewrite $s = 1/2 + 2\varepsilon + 2bi$ and denote $z = \varepsilon + bi$, then $s/2 = 1/4 + z$ and $(1-s)/2 = 1/4 - z$. To accord with

Figure 9: The variations of $U(1/4, t)e^{0.7t}$ and $V(1/4, t)e^{0.7t}$ with respect to $t \in [13, 51]$. The formulas in (10.5) with $N = 4$ and $K = 200$ are adopted.

the critical strap it requires $-1/4 \leq \varepsilon \leq 1/4$. In addition, the denotation $d_j = j + 1/4$ is also adopted.

It follows from (9.2) and (9.3) that

$$\begin{aligned}
-\xi_K(s) &= \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{2a_k}{\prod_{j=1}^k (s/2 + j)} + \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{2a_k}{\prod_{j=1}^k [(1-s)/2 + j]} \\
&= 2 \sum_{k=1}^K a_k \left[\frac{1}{\prod_{j=1}^k (d_j + z)} + \frac{1}{\prod_{j=1}^k (d_j - z)} \right] \\
&= 2 \sum_{k=1}^K a_k \frac{\prod_{j=1}^k (d_j - z) + \prod_{j=1}^k (d_j + z)}{\prod_{j=1}^k (d_j^2 - z^2)} \\
&= \frac{1}{\prod_{j=1}^K (d_j^2 - z^2)} \\
&\quad \cdot 2 \sum_{k=1}^K a_k \left[\prod_{j=1}^k (d_j - z) + \prod_{j=1}^k (d_j + z) \right] \prod_{j=k+1}^K (d_j^2 - z^2)
\end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{2A_K(z)}{B_K(z)}, \quad (11.2)$$

here we accept the supplementary definition $\prod_{j=k+1}^K (d_j^2 - z^2) = 1$ for the case with $k = K$. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} |\xi(s)|^2 &= \xi(s)\overline{\xi(s)} = \xi(s)\xi(\bar{s}) \\ &= \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \xi_K(s)\xi_K(\bar{s}) = \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{4A_K(z)A_K(\bar{z})}{B_K(z)B_K(\bar{z})}, \end{aligned} \quad (11.3)$$

where the reflection principle is used. For all K there must be

$$A_K(z)A_K(\bar{z}) = A_K(z)\overline{A_K(z)} \geq 0, \quad B_K(z)B_K(\bar{z}) = B_K(z)\overline{B_K(z)} \geq 0.$$

In fact, it can be proved that $B_K(z)B_K(\bar{z}) > 0$ for all $-1/4 \leq \varepsilon \leq 1/4$ and $-\infty < b < +\infty$. It follows from (11.2) that

$$\begin{aligned} B_K(z)B_K(\bar{z}) &= \prod_{j=1}^K (d_j^2 - z^2) \prod_{j=1}^K (d_j^2 - \bar{z}^2) \\ &= \prod_{j=1}^K [d_j^4 - (z^2 + \bar{z}^2)d_j^2 + (z\bar{z})^2] \\ &= \prod_{j=1}^K [d_j^4 + 2(b^2 - \varepsilon^2)d_j^2 + (b^2 + \varepsilon^2)^2] \\ &= \prod_{j=1}^K [(d_j^2 + b^2 - \varepsilon^2)^2 + 4b^2\varepsilon^2] > 0, \end{aligned} \quad (11.4)$$

since there is always $d_j^2 + b^2 - \varepsilon^2 > 0$ for $j \geq 1$.

The relations in (11.3) and (11.4) indicate that:

Proposition 11.1. *To prove the Riemann Hypothesis is equivalent to proving $\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} A_K(z)A_K(\bar{z}) > 0$ for the case with $\varepsilon \neq 0$, where $z = \varepsilon + bi$ with $-1/4 \leq \varepsilon \leq 1/4$ and $-\infty < b < +\infty$.*

To deal with $A_K(z)A_K(\bar{z})$, a natural thought is to make an expansion about ε . However, due to the complexity of the expressions, direct expansion is not suggested. We firstly consider $A_K(z)$.

12. To Expand $A_K(z)$ According to z

A combination number is used. To choose p elements from d_1, d_2, \dots, d_k and multiply them, the total sum is what we care about. Let i_n to be the n -th choice of i with $1 \leq i \leq k$. We require that i_n increases along with the increasing of n (different n accords with different i_n). For simplicity the total sum is denoted as

$$\alpha_{k,p} = \sum_{1 \leq i_n \leq k} \prod_{n=1}^p d_{i_n}, \quad 1 \leq p \leq k. \quad (12.1)$$

Particularly, $\alpha_{k,1} = \sum_{i=1}^k d_i$ and $\alpha_{k,k} = \prod_{i=1}^k d_i$. With these denotations we get an expansion (the first expansion formula) below:

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{j=1}^k (d_j + z) &= \alpha_{k,0} z^k + \alpha_{k,1} z^{k-1} + \alpha_{k,2} z^{k-2} \\ &\quad + \dots + \alpha_{k,k-1} z + \alpha_{k,k} \\ &= \sum_{m=0}^k \alpha_{k,k-m} z^m. \end{aligned} \quad (12.2)$$

Here a supplementary definition $\alpha_{k,0} = 1$ is added. This expansion holds for all the cases with $k \geq 1$. In case z is substituted by $-z$ the above expressions also hold.

Similarly, the combination number about $d_{k+1}^2, d_{k+2}^2, \dots, d_K^2$ is defined as follows:

$$\beta_{k,p} = \sum_{k+1 \leq i_n \leq K} \prod_{n=1}^p d_{i_n}^2, \quad 1 \leq p \leq K - k \quad (12.3)$$

with supplementary definition $\beta_{k,0} = 1$. The corresponding expansion is

$$\begin{aligned}
\prod_{j=k+1}^K (d_j^2 - z^2) &= \beta_{k,0}(-z^2)^{K-k} + \beta_{k,1}(-z^2)^{K-k-1} + \beta_{k,2}(-z^2)^{K-k-2} \\
&\quad + \cdots + \beta_{k,K-k-1}(-z^2) + \alpha_{k,K-k} \\
&= \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} (-1)^l \beta_{k,K-k-l} z^{2l}. \tag{12.4}
\end{aligned}$$

With the above expansion formulas, $A_K(z)$ can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned}
A_K(z) &= \sum_{k=1}^K a_k \left[\prod_{j=1}^k (d_j - z) + \prod_{j=1}^k (d_j + z) \right] \prod_{j=k+1}^K (d_j^2 - z^2) \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^K a_k \left[\sum_{m=0}^k (-1)^m \alpha_{k,k-m} z^m + \sum_{m=0}^k \alpha_{k,k-m} z^m \right] \\
&\quad \cdot \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} (-1)^l \beta_{k,K-k-l} z^{2l} \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^K a_k \sum_{m=0}^k [(-1)^m + 1] \alpha_{k,k-m} z^m \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} (-1)^l \beta_{k,K-k-l} z^{2l} \\
&= 2 \sum_{k=1}^K a_k \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \alpha_{k,k-2r} z^{2r} \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} (-1)^l \beta_{k,K-k-l} z^{2l} \\
&= 2 \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} (-1)^l a_k \alpha_{k,k-2r} \beta_{k,K-k-l} z^{2(l+r)} \\
&= 2 \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \sum_{n=l}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor + l} (-1)^l a_k \alpha_{k,k-2n+2l} \beta_{k,K-k-l} z^{2n}, \tag{12.5}
\end{aligned}$$

in which $\lfloor k/2 \rfloor$ means taking the integer part of $k/2$ with $\lfloor k/2 \rfloor \leq k/2$.

To exchange the orders of the series it related to two point $n = \lfloor k/2 \rfloor$ and $n = K - k$. The equality $k/2 = K - k$ yields $k = 2K/3$. To denote $M = \lfloor K/3 \rfloor$, for the cases with $K = 3M$, $3M + 1$ and $3M + 2$ the dividing

points are at $k_0 = 2M$, $2M + 2/3$ and $2M + 4/3$ respectively. In addition, we accept the denotation $\sum_{i=u}^v = 0$ for the case with $v < u$.

12.1. For the Case with $K = 3M$

Notice that the dividing point is at $k_0 = 2M$ for the case with $K = 3M$, to omit the general term we get

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \sum_{n=l}^{[k/2]+l} \\
= & \sum_{k=1}^{2M} \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \sum_{n=l}^{[k/2]+l} + \sum_{k=2M+1}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \sum_{n=l}^{[k/2]+l} \\
= & \sum_{k=1}^{2M} \sum_{n=0}^{[k/2]} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{k=1}^{2M-1} \sum_{n=[k/2]+1}^{K-k} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n \\
& + \sum_{k=2}^{2M} \sum_{n=K-k+1}^{K-k+[k/2]} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} + \sum_{k=2M+1}^K \sum_{n=0}^{K-k} \sum_{l=0}^n \\
& + \sum_{k=2M+1}^K \sum_{n=K-k+1}^{[k/2]} \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} + \sum_{k=2M+1}^{K-1} \sum_{n=[k/2]+1}^{K-k+[k/2]} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} \\
= & \sum_{n=0}^0 \sum_{k=1}^{2M} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{n=1}^M \sum_{k=2n}^{2M} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{n=1}^M \sum_{k=1}^{2n-1} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n \\
& + \sum_{n=M+1}^{K-1} \sum_{k=1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n + \sum_{n=M+1}^{2M} \sum_{k=K-n+1}^{2M} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} \\
& + \sum_{n=2M+1}^{K-1} \sum_{k=K-n+1}^{2(K-n)} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} + \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} \sum_{k=2M+1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=0}^n \\
& + \sum_{n=1}^M \sum_{k=K-n+1}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} + \sum_{n=M+1}^{[K/2]} \sum_{k=2n}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \\
& \sum_{n=M+1}^{[K/2]} \sum_{k=2M+1}^{2n-1} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} + \sum_{n=[K/2]+1}^{2M-1} \sum_{k=2M+1}^{2(K-n)} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{n=0}^0 \sum_{k=1}^{2M} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} \sum_{k=2M+1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=0}^n \\
&+ \sum_{n=1}^M \left[\sum_{k=1}^{2n-1} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n + \sum_{k=2n}^{2M} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{k=K-n+1}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=M+1}^{[K/2]} \sum_{k=2n}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} + \sum_{n=M+1}^{[K/2]} \sum_{k=2M+1}^{2n-1} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} \\
&+ \sum_{n=M+1}^{2M} \sum_{k=K-n+1}^{2M} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} + \sum_{n=M+1}^{K-1} \sum_{k=1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n \\
&+ \sum_{n=[K/2]+1}^{2M-1} \sum_{k=2M+1}^{2(K-n)} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} + \sum_{n=2M+1}^{K-1} \sum_{k=K-n+1}^{2(K-n)} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^0 \left[\sum_{k=1}^{2M} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{k=2M+1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=0}^n \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=1}^{M-1} \left[\sum_{k=1}^{2n-1} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n + \sum_{k=2n}^{2M} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{k=2M+1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{k=K-n+1}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=M}^M \left[\sum_{k=1}^{2n-1} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n + \sum_{k=2n}^{2M} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{k=K-n+1}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=M+1}^{[K/2]} \left[\sum_{k=1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n + \sum_{k=K-n+1}^{2M} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} + \sum_{k=2M+1}^{2n-1} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} + \sum_{k=2n}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=[K/2]+1}^{2M-1} \left[\sum_{k=1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n + \sum_{k=K-n+1}^{2M} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} + \sum_{k=2M+1}^{2(K-n)} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=2M}^{2M} \left[\sum_{k=1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n + \sum_{k=K-n+1}^{2M} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=2M+1}^{K-1} \left[\sum_{k=1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n + \sum_{k=K-n+1}^{2(K-n)} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{n=0}^0 \sum_{l=0}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-n} + \sum_{n=1}^{M-1} \left[\sum_{l=0}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=M}^M \left[\sum_{l=0}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] + \sum_{n=M+1}^{[K/2]} \left[\sum_{l=0}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=[K/2]+1}^{2M-1} \left[\sum_{l=2n-K}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=2M}^{2M} \left[\sum_{l=2n-K}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=2M+1}^{K-1} \left[\sum_{l=2n-K}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^0 \sum_{l=0}^0 \sum_{k=1}^K + \sum_{n=1}^{[K/2]} \left[\sum_{l=0}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=[K/2]+1}^{K-1} \left[\sum_{l=2n-K}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right]. \tag{12.6}
\end{aligned}$$

To denote $[K/2] = n_0$ and insert the above expression into (12.5) we get

$$\begin{aligned}
&\frac{1}{2} A_K(z) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^0 \sum_{l=0}^0 \sum_{k=1}^K (-1)^l a_k \alpha_{k,k-2n+2l} \beta_{k,K-k-l} z^{2n} \\
&+ \sum_{n=1}^{n_0} \left[\sum_{l=0}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] (-1)^l a_k \alpha_{k,k-2n+2l} \beta_{k,K-k-l} z^{2n} \\
&+ \sum_{n=n_0+1}^{K-1} \left[\sum_{l=2n-K}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] (-1)^l a_k \alpha_{k,k-2n+2l} \beta_{k,K-k-l} z^{2n} \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^K a_k \alpha_{k,k} \beta_{k,K-k} z^0
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \sum_{n=K-n_0}^{K-1} \left[\sum_{l=0}^{K-n-1} \sum_{k=2(K-n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=K-n}^{K-n} \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] \\
& \cdot (-1)^l a_k \alpha_{k,k-2(K-n-l)} \beta_{k,K-k-l} z^{2(K-n)} \\
& + \sum_{n=1}^{K-n_0-1} \left[\sum_{l=K-2n}^{K-n-1} \sum_{k=2(K-n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=K-n}^{K-n} \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] \\
& \cdot (-1)^l a_k \alpha_{k,k-2(K-n-l)} \beta_{k,K-k-l} z^{2(K-n)} \\
= & \sum_{n=1}^{K-n_0-1} \left[\sum_{l=1}^n \sum_{k=2l}^{n+l} + \sum_{l=0}^0 \sum_{k=1}^{n+l} \right] (-1)^{K-n-l} a_k \alpha_{k,k-2l} \beta_{k,n+l-k} z^{2(K-n)} \\
& + \sum_{n=K-n_0}^{K-1} \left[\sum_{l=1}^{K-n} \sum_{k=2l}^{n+l} + \sum_{l=0}^0 \sum_{k=1}^{n+l} \right] (-1)^{K-n-l} a_k \alpha_{k,k-2l} \beta_{k,n+l-k} z^{2(K-n)} \\
& + \sum_{k=1}^K a_k \alpha_{k,k} \beta_{k,K-k} z^0 \\
= & \sum_{n=1}^{K-n_0-1} \left[\sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{l=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} + \sum_{k=n+1}^{2n} \sum_{l=k-n}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \right] (-1)^{K-n-l} a_k \alpha_{k,k-2l} \beta_{k,n+l-k} z^{2(K-n)} \\
& + \sum_{n=K-n_0}^{K-1} \left[\sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{l=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} + \sum_{k=n+1}^{2(K-n)} \sum_{l=k-n}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} + \sum_{k=2(K-n)+1}^K \sum_{l=k-n}^{K-n} \right] \\
& \cdot (-1)^{K-n-l} a_k \alpha_{k,k-2l} \beta_{k,n+l-k} z^{2(K-n)} \\
& + \sum_{k=1}^K a_k \alpha_{k,k} \beta_{k,K-k} z^0 \\
= & \sum_{n=1}^{K-n_0-1} \left[\sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{l=k-\lfloor k/2 \rfloor}^k + \sum_{k=n+1}^{2n} \sum_{l=k-\lfloor k/2 \rfloor}^n \right] \\
& \cdot (-1)^{K-n-k+l} a_k \alpha_{k,2l-k} \beta_{k,n-l} z^{2(K-n)} \\
& + \sum_{n=K-n_0}^{K-1} \left[\sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{l=k-\lfloor k/2 \rfloor}^k + \sum_{k=n+1}^{2(K-n)} \sum_{l=k-\lfloor k/2 \rfloor}^n + \sum_{k=2(K-n)+1}^K \sum_{l=k-K+n}^n \right] \\
& \cdot (-1)^{K-n-k+l} a_k \alpha_{k,2l-k} \beta_{k,n-l} z^{2(K-n)}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \sum_{k=1}^K a_k \alpha_{k,k} \beta_{k,K-k} z^0 \\
= & \sum_{n=1}^{K-n_0-1} (-1)^{K-n} \left[\sum_{l=1}^n \sum_{k=l}^{2l} (-1)^{k-l} a_k \alpha_{k,2l-k} \beta_{k,n-l} \right] z^{2(K-n)} \\
& + \sum_{n=K-n_0}^{K-1} (-1)^{K-n} \left[\sum_{l=1}^{K-n} \sum_{k=l}^{2l} (-1)^{k-l} a_k \alpha_{k,2l-k} \beta_{k,n-l} \right. \\
& \left. + \sum_{l=K-n+1}^n \sum_{k=l}^{K-n+l} (-1)^{k-l} a_k \alpha_{k,2l-k} \beta_{k,n-l} \right] z^{2(K-n)} \\
& + \left[\sum_{k=1}^K a_k \alpha_{k,k} \beta_{k,K-k} \right] z^0 \tag{12.7} \\
= & \sum_{n=1}^{K-n_0-1} (-1)^{K-n} \left[\sum_{l=1}^n \sum_{k=l}^{2l} (-1)^{k-l} a_k \alpha_{k,2l-k} \beta_{k,n-l} \right] z^{2(K-n)} \\
& + \sum_{n=K-n_0}^{K-1} (-1)^{K-n} \left[\sum_{l=1}^{K-n} \sum_{k=l}^{2l} (-1)^{k-l} a_k \alpha_{k,2l-k} \beta_{k,n-l} \right] z^{2(K-n)} \\
& + \sum_{n=K-n_0}^K (-1)^{K-n} \left[\sum_{l=K-n+1}^n \sum_{k=l}^{K-n+l} (-1)^{k-l} a_k \alpha_{k,2l-k} \beta_{k,n-l} \right] z^{2(K-n)} \\
=: & \sum_{n=1}^{K-n_0-1} (-1)^{K-n} D_{1,n} z^{2(K-n)} + \sum_{n=K-n_0}^{K-1} (-1)^{K-n} D_{2,n} z^{2(K-n)} \\
& + \sum_{n=K-n_0}^K (-1)^{K-n} D_{3,n} z^{2(K-n)}. \tag{12.8}
\end{aligned}$$

Here we accept the additional definition that $\sum_{l=K-n+1}^n = \sum_{l=n_0+1}^{n_0} = 0$ for the even case with $K = 2n_0$.

12.2. For the Case with $K = 3M + 1$

Since for the case with $K = 3M + 1$ the dividing point is at $k_0 = 2M + 2/3$ (non-integer), for $k \leq 2M$ there is always $[k/2] < K - k$. In another word, there is no distribution on the line $k = k_0$. To repeat the deduction in (12.6)

we get

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \sum_{n=l}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor + l} \\
= & \sum_{k=1}^{2M} \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \sum_{n=l}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor + l} + \sum_{k=2M+1}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \sum_{n=l}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor + l} \\
= & \sum_{k=1}^{2M} \sum_{n=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{k=1}^{2M} \sum_{n=\lfloor k/2 \rfloor + 1}^{K-k} \sum_{l=n-\lfloor k/2 \rfloor}^n \\
& + \sum_{k=2}^{2M} \sum_{n=K-k+1}^{K-k+\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \sum_{l=n-\lfloor k/2 \rfloor}^{K-k} + \sum_{k=2M+1}^K \sum_{n=0}^{K-k} \sum_{l=0}^n \\
& + \sum_{k=2M+2}^K \sum_{n=K-k+1}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} + \sum_{k=2M+1}^{K-1} \sum_{n=\lfloor k/2 \rfloor + 1}^{K-k+\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \sum_{l=n-\lfloor k/2 \rfloor}^{K-k} \\
= & \sum_{n=0}^0 \sum_{k=1}^{2M} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{n=1}^M \sum_{k=2n}^{2M} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{n=1}^M \sum_{k=1}^{2n-1} \sum_{l=n-\lfloor k/2 \rfloor}^n \\
& + \sum_{n=M+1}^{K-1} \sum_{k=1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=n-\lfloor k/2 \rfloor}^n + \sum_{n=M+2}^{2M} \sum_{k=K-n+1}^{2M} \sum_{l=n-\lfloor k/2 \rfloor}^{K-k} \\
& + \sum_{n=2M+1}^{K-1} \sum_{k=K-n+1}^{2(K-n)} \sum_{l=n-\lfloor k/2 \rfloor}^{K-k} + \sum_{n=0}^M \sum_{k=2M+1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=0}^n \\
& + \sum_{n=1}^M \sum_{k=K-n+1}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} + \sum_{n=M+1}^{\lfloor K/2 \rfloor} \sum_{k=2n}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \\
& \sum_{n=M+1}^{\lfloor K/2 \rfloor} \sum_{k=2M+1}^{2n-1} \sum_{l=n-\lfloor k/2 \rfloor}^{K-k} + \sum_{n=\lfloor K/2 \rfloor + 1}^{2M} \sum_{k=2M+1}^{2(K-n)} \sum_{l=n-\lfloor k/2 \rfloor}^{K-k} \\
= & \sum_{n=0}^0 \left[\sum_{k=1}^{2M} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{k=2M+1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=0}^n \right] \\
& + \sum_{n=1}^M \left[\sum_{k=1}^{2n-1} \sum_{l=n-\lfloor k/2 \rfloor}^n + \sum_{k=2n}^{2M} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{k=2M+1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{k=K-n+1}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \sum_{n=M+1}^{M+1} \left[\sum_{k=1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n + \sum_{k=2M+1}^{2n-1} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} + \sum_{k=2n}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \right] \\
& + \sum_{n=M+2}^{[K/2]} \left[\sum_{k=1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n + \sum_{k=K-n+1}^{2M} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} + \sum_{k=2M+1}^{2n-1} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} + \sum_{k=2n}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \right] \\
& + \sum_{n=[K/2]+1}^{2M} \left[\sum_{k=1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n + \sum_{k=K-n+1}^{2M} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} + \sum_{k=2M+1}^{2(K-n)} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} \right] \\
& + \sum_{n=2M+1}^{K-1} \left[\sum_{k=1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n + \sum_{k=K-n+1}^{2(K-n)} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} \right] \\
& = \sum_{n=0}^0 \sum_{l=0}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-n} + \sum_{n=1}^M \left[\sum_{l=0}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] \\
& + \sum_{n=M+1}^{M+1} \left[\sum_{l=0}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] + \sum_{n=M+2}^{[K/2]} \left[\sum_{l=0}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] \\
& + \sum_{n=[K/2]+1}^{2M} \left[\sum_{l=2n-K}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] \\
& + \sum_{n=2M+1}^{K-1} \left[\sum_{l=2n-K}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] \\
& = \sum_{n=0}^0 \sum_{l=0}^0 \sum_{k=1}^K + \sum_{n=1}^{[K/2]} \left[\sum_{l=0}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] \\
& + \sum_{n=[K/2]+1}^{K-1} \left[\sum_{l=2n-K}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right], \tag{12.9}
\end{aligned}$$

which is same to (12.6) and the expression for $A_K(z)/2$ in (12.7) also holds for the case $K = 3M + 1$.

12.3. For the Case with $K = 3M + 2$

Since for the case with $K = 3M + 2$ the dividing point is at $k_0 = 2M + 4/3$ (non-integer), for $k \leq 2M + 1$ there is always $[k/2] < K - k$, and there is no distribution on the line $k = k_0$. To repeat the deduction in (12.6) we get

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \sum_{n=l}^{[k/2]+l} \\
= & \sum_{k=1}^{2M+1} \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \sum_{n=l}^{[k/2]+l} + \sum_{k=2M+2}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \sum_{n=l}^{[k/2]+l} \\
= & \sum_{k=1}^{2M+1} \sum_{n=0}^{[k/2]} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{k=1}^{2M+1} \sum_{n=[k/2]+1}^{K-k} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n \\
& + \sum_{k=2}^{2M+1} \sum_{n=K-k+1}^{K-k+[k/2]} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} + \sum_{k=2M+2}^K \sum_{n=0}^{K-k} \sum_{l=0}^n \\
& + \sum_{k=2M+2}^K \sum_{n=K-k+1}^{[k/2]} \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} + \sum_{k=2M+2}^{K-1} \sum_{n=[k/2]+1}^{K-k+[k/2]} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} \\
= & \sum_{n=0}^0 \sum_{k=1}^{2M+1} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{n=1}^M \sum_{k=2n}^{2M+1} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{n=1}^{M+1} \sum_{k=1}^{2n-1} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n \\
& + \sum_{n=M+2}^{K-1} \sum_{k=1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n + \sum_{n=M+2}^{2M+1} \sum_{k=K-n+1}^{2M} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} \\
& + \sum_{n=2M+2}^{K-1} \sum_{k=K-n+1}^{2(K-n)} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} + \sum_{n=0}^M \sum_{k=2M+2}^{K-n} \sum_{l=0}^n \\
& + \sum_{n=1}^M \sum_{k=K-n+1}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} + \sum_{n=M+1}^{[K/2]} \sum_{k=2n}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \\
& \sum_{n=M+2}^{[K/2]} \sum_{k=2M+1}^{2n-1} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} + \sum_{n=[K/2]+1}^{2M+1} \sum_{k=2M+1}^{2(K-n)} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{n=0}^0 \left[\sum_{k=1}^{2M+1} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{k=2M+2}^{K-n} \sum_{l=0}^n \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=1}^M \left[\sum_{k=1}^{2n-1} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n + \sum_{k=2n}^{2M+1} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{k=2M+2}^{K-n} \sum_{l=0}^n + \sum_{k=K-n+1}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=M+1}^{M+1} \left[\sum_{k=1}^{2n-1} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n + \sum_{k=2n}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=M+2}^{[K/2]} \left[\sum_{k=1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n + \sum_{k=K-n+1}^{2M} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} + \sum_{k=2M+1}^{2n-1} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} + \sum_{k=2n}^K \sum_{l=0}^{K-k} \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=[K/2]+1}^{2M+1} \left[\sum_{k=1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n + \sum_{k=K-n+1}^{2M} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} + \sum_{k=2M+1}^{2(K-n)} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=2M+2}^{K-1} \left[\sum_{k=1}^{K-n} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^n + \sum_{k=K-n+1}^{2(K-n)} \sum_{l=n-[k/2]}^{K-k} \right] \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^0 \sum_{l=0}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-n} + \sum_{n=1}^M \left[\sum_{l=0}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=M+1}^{M+1} \left[\sum_{l=0}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] + \sum_{n=M+2}^{[K/2]} \left[\sum_{l=0}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=[K/2]+1}^{2M+1} \left[\sum_{l=2n-K}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] \\
&+ \sum_{n=2M+2}^{K-1} \left[\sum_{l=2n-K}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right] \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^0 \sum_{l=0}^0 \sum_{k=1}^K + \sum_{n=1}^{[K/2]} \left[\sum_{l=0}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$+ \sum_{n=[K/2]+1}^{K-1} \left[\sum_{l=2n-K}^{n-1} \sum_{k=2(n-l)}^{K-l} + \sum_{l=n}^n \sum_{k=1}^{K-l} \right], \quad (12.10)$$

which is same to (12.6) and the expression for $A_K(z)/2$ in (12.7) also holds for the case $K = 3M + 2$.

12.4. The Expansion Formula of $A_K(z)$

The previous 3 sub-sections show that for the cases with $K = 3M$, $3M+1$ and $3M + 2$ the expressions of $A_K(z)/2$ are the same one. That is to say, the expansion of $A_K(z)/2$ does not rely on $M = [K/3]$. Its final expansion formula is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2}A_K(z) &= \sum_{n=1}^{K-n_0-1} (-1)^{K-n} D_{1,n} z^{2(K-n)} \\ &\quad + \sum_{n=K-n_0}^{K-1} (-1)^{K-n} D_{2,n} z^{2(K-n)} \\ &\quad + \sum_{n=K-n_0}^K (-1)^{K-n} D_{3,n} z^{2(K-n)}, \end{aligned} \quad (12.11)$$

in which $n_0 = [K/2]$ and

$$\begin{aligned} D_{1,n} &= \sum_{l=1}^n \sum_{k=l}^{2l} (-1)^{k-l} a_k \alpha_{k,2l-k} \beta_{k,n-l}, \\ D_{2,n} &= \sum_{l=1}^{K-n} \sum_{k=l}^{2l} (-1)^{k-l} a_k \alpha_{k,2l-k} \beta_{k,n-l}, \\ D_{3,n} &= \sum_{l=K-n+1}^n \sum_{k=l}^{K-n+l} (-1)^{k-l} a_k \alpha_{k,2l-k} \beta_{k,n-l}. \end{aligned} \quad (12.12)$$

Here the additional definition $\sum_{l=K-n+1}^n = \sum_{l=n_0+1}^{n_0} = 0$ is adopted for the even case with $K = 2n_0$.

This indicates that $A_K(z)$ only contains the even powers of z , and in case z is substituted by $-z$ its form maintains unchanged. In the following we calculate $D_{1,n}$, $D_{2,n}$ and $D_{3,n}$ term by term. Before doing so, the relationship of the coefficients needs to be clarified.

13. The Relationship of a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k with $2 \leq k \leq K$

To trace back to the definitions in (8.2) and (9.2), there is

$$\begin{aligned} a_k &= (k + \frac{1}{2})C_k - C_{k+1} = (-1)^k f^{(k)}(1) \\ &= (-1)^k [(k + \frac{1}{2})\varphi^{(k)}(1) + \varphi^{(k+1)}(1)] \end{aligned} \quad (13.1)$$

with $f(x) = \varphi(x)/2 + x\varphi'(x)$ and $\varphi(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2\pi x}$ which satisfies the equality in (1.5):

$$\varphi(x) + \frac{1}{2} = x^{-1/2} \left[\varphi(x^{-1}) + \frac{1}{2} \right]. \quad (13.2)$$

13.1. The General Relation of the Derivative Functions

It follows from (13.2) that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2}\varphi(x) + x\varphi'(x) &= \frac{1}{2} \left[x^{-1/2}\varphi(u) + \frac{1}{2}x^{-1/2} - \frac{1}{2} \right] \\ &\quad - x \left[\frac{1}{2}x^{-3/2}\varphi(u) + x^{-5/2}\varphi'(u) + \frac{1}{4}x^{-3/2} \right] \\ &= -x^{-3/2}\varphi'(u) - \frac{1}{4} \end{aligned}$$

with $u = x^{-1}$. Its derivative reads:

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\frac{1}{2}\varphi(x) + x\varphi'(x) \right]' &= \frac{3}{2}x^{-5/2}\varphi'(u) + x^{-7/2}\varphi''(u) \\ &= x^{-5/2} \left[\frac{3}{2}\varphi'(u) + u\varphi''(u) \right], \end{aligned}$$

that is,

$$f'(x)x^{5/2} = f'(x^{-1}). \quad (13.3)$$

Notice that the general expression for the k -th derivative of $f(x^{-1})$ is too complex to calculate, to take the derivative of (13.3) time by time is undesirable. Here we adopt another approach. To denote $F_1(x) = f'(x)x^{5/2}$, $F_2(x) = F_1'(x)x^2$, $F_3(x) = F_2'(x)x^2$, \dots , $F_k(x) = F_{k-1}'(x)x^2$, then it is easily checked that

$$\begin{aligned} F_2(x) &= [f'(x^{-1})]'x^2 = -f''(x^{-1}), \\ F_3(x) &= [-f''(x^{-1})]'x^2 = f'''(x^{-1}), \\ &\vdots \\ F_k(x) &= [(-1)^{k-2}f^{(k)}(x^{-1})]'x^2 = (-1)^{k-1}f^{(k)}(x^{-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (13.4)$$

and the calculating work can be greatly simplified. It only needs to calculate $F_k(x)$ with the iteration relation. The first several terms are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} F_2(x) &= [f'(x)x^{5/2}]'x^2 \\ &= \left[f''(x)x^{5/2} + \frac{5}{2}f'(x)x^{3/2} \right]x^2 \\ &= f''(x)x^{9/2} + \frac{5}{2}f'(x)x^{7/2}. \\ F_3(x) &= \left[f''(x)x^{9/2} + \frac{5}{2}f'(x)x^{7/2} \right]'x^2 \\ &= \left[f'''(x)x^{9/2} + \left(\frac{9}{2} + \frac{5}{2}\right)f''(x)x^{7/2} + \frac{5}{2} \cdot \frac{7}{2}f'(x)x^{5/2} \right]x^2 \\ &= f'''(x)x^{13/2} + \left(\frac{9}{2} + \frac{5}{2}\right)f''(x)x^{11/2} + \frac{5}{2} \cdot \frac{7}{2}f'(x)x^{9/2}. \\ F_4(x) &= \left[f'''(x)x^{13/2} + \left(\frac{9}{2} + \frac{5}{2}\right)f''(x)x^{11/2} + \frac{5}{2} \cdot \frac{7}{2}f'(x)x^{9/2} \right]'x^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= f^{(4)}(x)x^{17/2} + \left(\frac{13}{2} + \frac{9}{2} + \frac{5}{2}\right)f'''(x)x^{15/2} \\
&\quad + \left[\left(\frac{9}{2} + \frac{5}{2}\right)\frac{11}{2} + \frac{5}{2} \cdot \frac{7}{2}\right]f''(x)x^{13/2} + \frac{5}{2} \cdot \frac{7}{2} \cdot \frac{9}{2}f'(x)x^{11/2}. \\
F_5(x) &= f^{(5)}(x)x^{21/2} + \left(\frac{17}{2} + \frac{13}{2} + \frac{9}{2} + \frac{5}{2}\right)f^{(4)}(x)x^{19/2} \\
&\quad + \left[\left(\frac{13}{2} + \frac{9}{2} + \frac{5}{2}\right)\frac{15}{2} + \left(\frac{9}{2} + \frac{5}{2}\right)\frac{11}{2} + \frac{5}{2} \cdot \frac{7}{2}\right]f'''(x)x^{17/2} \\
&\quad + \left\{\left[\left(\frac{9}{2} + \frac{5}{2}\right)\frac{11}{2} + \frac{5}{2} \cdot \frac{7}{2}\right]\frac{13}{2} + \frac{5}{2} \cdot \frac{7}{2} \cdot \frac{9}{2}\right\}f''(x)x^{15/2} \\
&\quad + \frac{5}{2} \cdot \frac{7}{2} \cdot \frac{9}{2} \cdot \frac{11}{2}f'(x)x^{13/2}.
\end{aligned}$$

Generally, for an arbitrary $k (\geq 1)$, if it satisfies

$$F_k(x) = \sum_{j=1}^k \lambda_{k,j} f^{(j)}(x) x^{k+j+1/2}, \quad (13.5)$$

in which $\lambda_{k,1} = \prod_{l=2}^k (l + 1/2)$ (for $k \geq 2$), $\lambda_{k,k} = 1$, and $\lambda_{k,j} = \lambda_{k-1,j-1} + (k + j - 1/2)\lambda_{k-1,j}$ for $k \geq 3$ and $2 \leq j \leq k - 1$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
F_{k+1}(x) &= F'_k(x)x^2 \\
&= \sum_{j=1}^k \lambda_{k,j} f^{(j+1)}(x) x^{k+j+1/2} \cdot x^2 \\
&\quad + \sum_{j=1}^k \left(k + j + \frac{1}{2}\right) \lambda_{k,j} f^{(j)}(x) x^{k+j-1/2} \cdot x^2 \\
&= \sum_{j=2}^{k+1} \lambda_{k,j-1} f^{(j)}(x) x^{k+1+j+1/2} \\
&\quad + \sum_{j=1}^k \left(k + j + \frac{1}{2}\right) \lambda_{k,j} f^{(j)}(x) x^{k+1+j+1/2} \\
&:= \sum_{j=1}^{k+1} \lambda_{k+1,j} f^{(j)}(x) x^{k+1+j+1/2} \quad (13.6)
\end{aligned}$$

with $\lambda_{k+1,1} = (k+1+1/2)\lambda_{k,1} = \prod_{l=2}^{k+1}(l+1/2)$, $\lambda_{k+1,k+1} = \lambda_{k,k} = 1$ and $\lambda_{k+1,j} = \lambda_{k,j-1} + (k+1+j-1/2)\lambda_{k,j}$ for the cases with $2 \leq j \leq k$. That is to say, if the expression holds for the case with k , it also holds for the case with $k+1$. The mathematical-induction method indicates that (13.5) is the general formula for $F_k(x)$. As for the coefficients, a natural result of the iteration relation is that

$$\lambda_{k,k-1} = \sum_{l=1}^{k-1} \left(2l + \frac{1}{2}\right), \quad k \geq 2. \quad (13.7)$$

To differ from the existing denotation $d_l = l+1/4$, we denote $d_l^* = l+1/2$. These two denotations have the relation $d_{2l}^* = 2d_l$. The two known series can be rewritten as $\lambda_{k,1} = \prod_{l=2}^k d_l^*$ and $\lambda_{k,k-1} = \sum_{l=1}^{k-1} d_{2l}^* = (k-1)d_k^*$. In view that the series $\{d_l\}_l^k$ is an arithmetic progression, for the case with $j=2$, it follows from the iteration relation $\lambda_{k,2} = \lambda_{k-1,1} + d_{k+1}^* \lambda_{k-1,2}$ that

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{3,2} &= \lambda_{2,1} + d_4^* \lambda_{2,2} = d_2^* + d_4^* = 2d_3^*, \\ \lambda_{4,2} &= \lambda_{3,1} + d_5^* \lambda_{3,2} = d_2^* d_3^* + 2d_5^* d_3^* = 3d_3^* d_4^*, \\ \lambda_{5,2} &= \lambda_{4,1} + d_6^* \lambda_{4,2} = d_2^* d_3^* d_4^* + d_6^* d_3^* (d_2^* + 2d_5^*) = 4 \prod_{l=3}^5 d_l^*, \\ \lambda_{6,2} &= \lambda_{5,1} + d_7^* \lambda_{5,2} = \prod_{l=2}^5 d_l^* + 4d_7^* \prod_{l=3}^5 d_l^* = 5 \prod_{l=3}^6 d_l^*, \\ \lambda_{7,2} &= \lambda_{6,1} + d_8^* \lambda_{6,2} = \prod_{l=2}^6 d_l^* + d_8^* \prod_{l=3}^5 d_l^* (d_2^* + 4d_7^*) = 6 \prod_{l=3}^7 d_l^*. \end{aligned}$$

To use the mathematical-induction method we get the general formula for $k \geq 3$:

$$\lambda_{k,2} = G_{k,2} \prod_{l=3}^k d_l^* \quad (13.8)$$

with $G_{k,2} = k - 1$. By the way, to rewrite $\lambda_{k,1} = G_{k,1} \prod_{l=2}^k d_l^*$, then $G_{k,1} \equiv 1$.

One step further, for the case with $j = 3$, the iteration relation becomes $\lambda_{k,3} = \lambda_{k-1,2} + d_{k+2}^* \lambda_{k-1,3}$ and

$$\begin{aligned}
\lambda_{4,3} &= 3d_4^*, \\
\lambda_{5,3} &= \lambda_{4,2} + d_7^* \lambda_{4,3} = 3d_3^* d_4^* + 3d_4^* d_7^* = (3 + 3)d_4^* d_5^*, \\
\lambda_{6,3} &= \lambda_{5,2} + d_8^* \lambda_{5,3} = \prod_{l=4}^5 d_l^* (4d_3^* + 6d_8^*) = (4 + 6) \prod_{l=4}^6 d_l^*, \\
\lambda_{7,3} &= \lambda_{6,2} + d_9^* \lambda_{6,3} = 5 \prod_{l=3}^6 d_l^* + 10d_9^* \prod_{l=4}^6 d_l^* = (5 + 10) \prod_{l=4}^7 d_l^*, \\
\lambda_{8,3} &= \lambda_{7,2} + d_{10}^* \lambda_{7,3} = 6 \prod_{l=3}^7 d_l^* + 15d_{10}^* \prod_{l=4}^7 d_l^* = (6 + 15) \prod_{l=4}^8 d_l^*, \\
\lambda_{9,3} &= (7 + 21) \prod_{l=4}^9 d_l^*, \quad \lambda_{10,3} = (8 + 28) \prod_{l=4}^{10} d_l^*, \\
\lambda_{11,3} &= (9 + 36) \prod_{l=4}^{11} d_l^*. \tag{13.9}
\end{aligned}$$

It follows from the mathematical-induction method that the general formula for $k \geq 4$ is

$$\lambda_{k,3} = G_{k,3} \prod_{l=4}^k d_l^* \tag{13.10}$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{k,3} &= G_{k-1,2} + G_{k-1,3} = (k - 2) + [(k - 3) + G_{k-2,3}] \\
&= (k - 2) + (k - 3) + \cdots + 3 + G_{4,3} \\
&= (k - 2) + (k - 3) + \cdots + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
&= \sum_{n=1}^{k-2} n = \frac{1}{2!} \prod_{p=1}^2 (k - p) = C_{k-1}^2,
\end{aligned}$$

where C_{k-1}^2 is the combination number defined in the previous.

Similarly, we get

$$\lambda_{k,4} = G_{k,4} \prod_{l=5}^k d_l^* \quad (13.11)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} G_{k,4} &= G_{k-1,3} + G_{k-1,4} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(k-3)(k-2) + \frac{1}{2}(k-4)(k-3) + \cdots + \frac{1}{2}1 \cdot 2 \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{k-3} \frac{n(n+1)}{2} = \frac{1}{3!} \prod_{p=1}^3 (k-p) = C_{k-1}^3. \end{aligned}$$

Generally, for $k \geq 2$ and $1 \leq j \leq k-1$ if it holds

$$\lambda_{k,j} = C_{k-1}^{j-1} \prod_{l=j+1}^k d_l^*, \quad (13.12)$$

then it follows from the known iteration relation that

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{k+1,j} &= \lambda_{k,j-1} + d_{k+j}^* \lambda_{k,j} \\ &= C_{k-1}^{j-2} \prod_{l=j}^k d_l^* + d_{k+j}^* C_{k-1}^{j-1} \prod_{l=j+1}^k d_l^* \\ &= (C_{k-1}^{j-2} d_j^* + C_{k-1}^{j-1} d_{k+j}^*) \prod_{l=j+1}^k d_l^* \\ &= (C_{k-1}^{j-2} + C_{k-1}^{j-1}) d_{k+1}^* \prod_{l=j+1}^k d_l^* \\ &\quad + [C_{k-1}^{j-2}(k-j+1) - C_{k-1}^{j-1}(j-1)] \prod_{l=j+1}^k d_l^* \\ &= C_k^{j-1} \prod_{l=j+1}^{k+1} d_l^* + 0, \end{aligned}$$

here the rule of addition: $C_{k-1}^{j-2} + C_{k-1}^{j-1} = C_k^{j-1}$ is used. This indicates the expression also holds for $k + 1$ and (13.12) is indeed the general formula for $\lambda_{k,j}$.

To combine the expressions in (13.4) and (13.5) we get the final relation:

$$\sum_{j=1}^k \lambda_{k,j} f^{(j)}(x) x^{k+j+1/2} = (-1)^{k-1} f^{(k)}(x^{-1}). \quad (13.13)$$

13.2. The Relationship of a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k

For the particular case with $x = 1$ the equation in (13.13) reads:

$$\sum_{j=1}^k \lambda_{k,j} f^{(j)}(1) = (-1)^{k-1} f^{(k)}(1).$$

Furthermore, in view of $\lambda_{k,k} \equiv 1$ to substitute $(-1)^j f^{(j)}(1)$ by a_j and insert (13.12) in it we get

$$\sum_{j=1}^{k-1} (-1)^j C_{k-1}^{j-1} \prod_{l=j+1}^k d_l^* a_j + \chi_k a_k = 0. \quad (13.14)$$

with $\chi_k = 1 + (-1)^k$. Notice that the highest term in the above expression disappears for the odd case with $k = 2m + 1$ and losses its representative, we summary the results for the even case with $k = 2m$.

Theorem 13.1. *The numbers a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{2m} ($m \geq 1$) defined in Theorem 9.1 satisfy the relationship:*

$$\sum_{j=1}^{2m-1} (-1)^j \left[C_{2m-1}^{j-1} \prod_{l=j+1}^{2m} d_l^* \right] a_j + 2a_{2m} = 0, \quad (13.15)$$

with $d_l^* = l + 1/2$.

Though the odd cases have no representative, they are helpful for simplifying the even equations. The first 5 equations of (13.14) with respect to $k = 2, 3, 4, 5, 6$ are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
0 &= -d_2^* a_1 + 2a_2. \\
0 &= -d_2^* d_3^* a_1 + 2d_3^* a_2 + 0a_3. \\
0 &= -\prod_{l=2}^4 d_l^* a_1 + 3 \prod_{l=3}^4 d_l^* a_2 - 3d_4^* a_3 + 2a_4 \\
&\quad -d_4^* (-d_2^* d_3^* a_1 + 2d_3^* a_2) \\
&= d_3^* d_4^* a_2 - 3d_4^* a_3 + 2a_4. \\
0 &= -\prod_{l=2}^5 d_l^* a_1 + 4 \prod_{l=3}^5 d_l^* a_2 - 6 \prod_{l=4}^5 d_l^* a_3 + 4d_5^* a_4 + 0a_5 \\
&\quad -d_5^* \left[-\prod_{l=2}^4 d_l^* a_1 + 3 \prod_{l=3}^4 d_l^* a_2 - 3d_4^* a_3 + 2a_4 \right] \\
&= \prod_{l=3}^5 d_l^* a_2 - 3 \prod_{l=4}^5 d_l^* a_3 + 2d_5^* a_4. \\
0 &= -\prod_{l=2}^6 d_l^* a_1 + 5 \prod_{l=3}^6 d_l^* a_2 - 10 \prod_{l=4}^6 d_l^* a_3 + 10 \prod_{l=5}^6 d_l^* a_4 - 5d_6^* a_5 + 2a_6 \\
&\quad -d_6^* \left[-\prod_{l=2}^5 d_l^* a_1 + 4 \prod_{l=3}^5 d_l^* a_2 - 6 \prod_{l=4}^5 d_l^* a_3 + 4d_5^* a_4 \right] \\
&= \prod_{l=3}^6 d_l^* a_2 - 4 \prod_{l=4}^6 d_l^* a_3 + 6 \prod_{l=5}^6 d_l^* a_4 - 5d_6^* a_5 + 2a_6 \\
&\quad -d_6^* \left[\prod_{l=3}^5 d_l^* a_2 - 3 \prod_{l=4}^5 d_l^* a_3 + 2d_5^* a_4 \right] \\
&= -\prod_{l=4}^6 d_l^* a_3 + 4 \prod_{l=5}^6 d_l^* a_4 - 5d_6^* a_5 + 2a_6.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0 &= \sum_{j=1}^7 (-1)^j \left[C_7^{j-1} \prod_{l=j+1}^8 d_l^* \right] a_j + 2a_8 \\
&= \prod_{l=5}^8 d_l^* a_4 - 5 \prod_{l=6}^8 d_l^* a_5 + 9 \prod_{l=7}^8 d_l^* a_6 - 7d_8^* a_7 + 2a_8.
\end{aligned} \tag{13.16}$$

We note here that the expression which includes a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4 is uncertain, since any multiple of $-d_2^* a_1 + 2a_2$ can be added. To substitute $d_2^* a_1$ by $2a_2$, the expression becomes a certain one. The same things occur for the successors. To get a certain relationship, a better choice is to reform the equations.

To observe the listed even equations (with $k = 2m$) in (13.16) we know that, except the first one with $m = 1$, the renewed ones only contain the numbers $a_m, a_{m+1} \cdots a_{2m}$. Let m be a fixed positive integer with $m \geq 2$, then for all $2 \leq k \leq 2m$ the equations in (13.14) can be rewritten in the unified form:

$$\sum_{j=1}^{k-1} C_{k-1}^{j-1} A_j + \chi_k A_k = 0, \tag{13.17}$$

with $A_j = (-1)^j \prod_{l=j+1}^{2m} d_l^* a_j$ ($1 \leq j \leq k-1$) and $A_k = \prod_{l=k+1}^{2m} d_l^* a_k$. Here an additional definition $\prod_{l=u}^v d_l^* = 1$ is adopted for the case with $v < u$. In view of the rule of addition $C_n^p = C_{n-1}^p + C_{n-1}^{p-1}$ ($p < n$), to subtract the $(k-1)$ -th equation from the k -th equation time by time we can get the renewed ones. For simplicity, we denote $\gamma_{p,p}^{(i)} = \chi_p$, $\gamma_{k,k-i}^{(i)} = C_{k-i}^{k-2i}$ for $j = k-i$, and

$$\gamma_{k,j}^{(i+1)} = \gamma_{k,j}^{(i)} - \gamma_{k-1,j}^{(i)} \tag{13.18}$$

for $k - i < j < k$ (with $i \geq 1$ and $p \geq 2$). The detained deduction process is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
0 &= \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} C_{k-1}^{j-1} A_j + \gamma_{k,k}^{(1)} A_k - \left[\sum_{j=1}^{k-2} C_{k-2}^{j-1} A_j + \gamma_{k-1,k-1}^{(1)} A_{k-1} \right] \\
&= \sum_{j=2}^{k-2} C_{k-2}^{j-2} A_j + (C_{k-1}^{k-2} - \gamma_{k-1,k-1}^{(1)}) A_{k-1} + \gamma_{k,k}^{(1)} A_k \\
&= \sum_{j=2}^{k-2} C_{k-2}^{j-2} A_j + \gamma_{k,k-1}^{(2)} A_{k-1} + \gamma_{k,k}^{(2)} A_k \\
&= \sum_{j=2}^{k-2} C_{k-2}^{j-2} A_j + \gamma_{k,k-1}^{(2)} A_{k-1} + \gamma_{k,k}^{(2)} A_k \\
&\quad - \left[\sum_{j=2}^{k-3} C_{k-3}^{j-2} A_j + \gamma_{k-1,k-2}^{(2)} A_{k-2} + \gamma_{k-1,k-1}^{(2)} A_{k-1} \right] \\
&= \sum_{j=3}^{k-3} C_{k-3}^{j-3} A_j + (C_{k-2}^{k-4} - \gamma_{k-1,k-2}^{(2)}) A_{k-2} \\
&\quad + (\gamma_{k,k-1}^{(2)} - \gamma_{k-1,k-1}^{(2)}) A_{k-1} + \gamma_{k,k}^{(2)} A_k \\
&= \sum_{j=3}^{k-3} C_{k-3}^{j-3} A_j + \gamma_{k,k-2}^{(3)} A_{k-2} + \gamma_{k,k-1}^{(3)} A_{k-1} + \gamma_{k,k}^{(3)} A_k \\
&\quad \vdots \\
&= A_m + \gamma_{2m,m+1}^{(m)} A_{m+1} + \cdots + \gamma_{2m,2m-1}^{(m)} A_{2m-1} + \gamma_{2m,2m}^{(m)} A_{2m} \\
&= \sum_{p=0}^m \gamma_{2m,2m-p}^{(m)} A_{2m-p} \tag{13.19}
\end{aligned}$$

for the case with $k = 2m$ (to expand until $j = m$). The trivial cases are $\gamma_{2m,2m}^{(m)} = \chi_{2m} = 2$ and $\gamma_{2m,m}^{(m)} = 1$.

Under the forms of (13.17), to observe the listed equations in (13.16) we find that the one for $k = 3$ is same to that for $k = 2$ without deduction, the one for $k = 5$ is same to that for $k = 4$ after once deduction. That is to say,

the coefficients $\gamma_{3,j}^{(1)} = \gamma_{2,j}^{(1)}$ (for $1 \leq j \leq 2$) and $\gamma_{5,j}^{(2)} = \gamma_{4,j}^{(2)}$ (for $2 \leq j \leq 4$) are the final forms for them. Particularly, for the even cases $k = 2m$ with $m = 1, 2, 3$ and 4 , their coefficients are in the unified form:

$$\gamma_{2m,2m-p}^{(m)} = \frac{1}{p} C_{2m-p}^1 C_{m-1}^{p-1} \quad (13.20)$$

for $1 \leq p \leq m$. For $m \geq 5$, there is

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{2m,2m-1}^{(m)} &= \gamma_{2m,2m-1}^{(m-1)} - \gamma_{2m-1,2m-1}^{(m-1)} \\ &= \gamma_{2m,2m-1}^{(m-2)} - \gamma_{2m-1,2m-1}^{(m-2)} - \gamma_{2m-1,2m-1}^{(m-1)} \\ &= \gamma_{2m,2m-1}^{(1)} - \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} \gamma_{2m-1,2m-1}^{(i)} \\ &= C_{2m-1}^{2m-2} - C_{m-1}^1 \chi_{2m-1} = C_{2m-1}^1 C_{m-1}^0. \end{aligned}$$

In general there is $\gamma_{k,k-1}^{(q)} = C_{k-1}^{k-2} - C_{q-1}^1 \chi_{k-1}$ for all $2 \leq q \leq m$. To substitute k by $k-1$ we get $\gamma_{k-1,k-2}^{(q)} = C_{k-2}^{k-3} - C_{q-1}^1 \chi_{k-2}$. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{2m,2m-2}^{(m)} &= \gamma_{2m,2m-2}^{(2)} - \sum_{i=2}^{m-1} \gamma_{2m-1,2m-2}^{(i)} \\ &= C_{2m-2}^{2m-4} - \sum_{i=2}^{m-1} [C_{2m-2}^{2m-3} - C_{i-1}^1 \chi_{2m-2}] \\ &= C_{2m-2}^{2m-4} - C_{m-2}^1 C_{2m-2}^{2m-3} + C_{m-1}^2 \chi_{2m-2} \\ &= (m-1)^2 = \frac{1}{2} C_{2m-2}^1 C_{m-1}^1, \end{aligned}$$

and there are $\gamma_{k,k-2}^{(q)} = C_{k-2}^{k-4} - C_{q-2}^1 C_{k-2}^{k-3} + C_{q-1}^2 \chi_{k-2}$ and $\gamma_{k-1,k-3}^{(q)} = C_{k-3}^{k-5} - C_{q-2}^1 C_{k-3}^{k-4} + C_{q-1}^2 \chi_{k-3}$. One step further,

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{2m,2m-3}^{(m)} &= \gamma_{2m,2m-3}^{(3)} - \sum_{i=3}^{m-1} \gamma_{2m-1,2m-3}^{(i)} \\ &= C_{2m-3}^{2m-6} - \sum_{i=3}^{m-1} [C_{2m-3}^{2m-5} - C_{i-2}^1 C_{2m-3}^{2m-4} + C_{i-1}^2 \chi_{2m-3}] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= C_{2m-3}^{2m-6} - C_{m-3}^1 C_{2m-3}^{2m-5} + C_{m-2}^2 C_{2m-3}^{2m-4} - C_{m-1}^3 \chi_{2m-3} \\
&= \frac{1}{6}(2m-3)(m-1)(m-2) = \frac{1}{3} C_{2m-3}^1 C_{m-1}^2.
\end{aligned}$$

To use another rule of addition $\sum_{i=0}^k C_{\alpha+i}^i = C_{\alpha+k+1}^k$, for all $l \geq 2$ and $1 \leq r \leq l-1$ we get that

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i=l}^{m-1} C_{i-l+r}^r &= \sum_{i=0}^{m-1-l} C_{r+i}^r = \sum_{i=0}^{m-1-l} C_{r+i}^i \\
&= C_{r+m-l}^{m-l-1} = C_{r+m-l}^{r+1}.
\end{aligned} \tag{13.21}$$

By using the mathematical-induction method again we get the general expression for $1 \leq p \leq m-2$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\gamma_{2m,2m-p}^{(m)} &= \sum_{i=0}^{p-1} (-1)^i C_{m-p+i-1}^i C_{2m-p}^{p-i} + (-1)^p C_{m-1}^p \chi_{2m-p} \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^p (-1)^{p-i} C_{m-1-i}^{p-i} C_{2m-p}^i + (-1)^p C_{m-1}^p \chi_{2m-p}.
\end{aligned} \tag{13.22}$$

To substitute $2m-p$ by j it results in

$$\gamma_{2m,j}^{(m)} = \sum_{i=1}^{2m-j} (-1)^{i+j} C_{m-i-1}^{j-m-1} C_j^i + (-1)^j C_{m-1}^{j-m-1} \chi_j \tag{13.23}$$

with $m+2 \leq j \leq 2m-1$. In case p is an even number there are

$$\begin{aligned}
\gamma_{2(m-1),j-1}^{(m-1)} &= \sum_{i=1}^{2m-j-1} (-1)^{i+j-1} C_{m-i-2}^{j-m-1} C_{j-1}^i, \\
\gamma_{2(m-1),j-2}^{(m-1)} &= \sum_{i=1}^{2m-j} (-1)^{i+j} C_{m-i-2}^{j-m-2} C_{j-2}^i + 2C_{m-2}^{j-m-2}.
\end{aligned}$$

They may have some relationship with $\gamma_{2m,j}^{(m)}$. In fact,

$$\gamma_{2m,j}^{(m)} = \sum_{i=1}^{2m-j} (-1)^{i+j} C_{m-i-1}^{j-m-1} C_j^i + 2C_{m-1}^{j-m-1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{i=1}^{2m-j} (-1)^{i+j} C_{m-i-1}^{j-m-1} [C_{j-1}^i + C_{j-1}^{i-1}] + 2C_{m-1}^{j-m-1} \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^{2m-j} (-1)^{i+j} C_{m-i-1}^{j-m-1} C_{j-1}^i + 2C_{m-1}^{j-m-1} \\
&\quad + \sum_{i=1}^{2m-j-1} (-1)^{i+j-1} C_{m-i-2}^{j-m-1} C_{j-1}^i - C_{m-2}^{j-m-1} \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^{2m-j} (-1)^{i+j} C_{m-i-1}^{j-m-1} [C_{j-2}^i + C_{j-2}^{i-1}] \\
&\quad + 2C_{m-1}^{j-m-1} + \gamma_{2(m-1),j-1}^{(m-1)} - C_{m-2}^{j-m-1} \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^{2m-j} (-1)^{i+j} C_{m-i-1}^{j-m-1} C_{j-2}^i \\
&\quad + \sum_{i=1}^{2m-j-1} (-1)^{i+j-1} C_{m-i-2}^{j-m-1} C_{j-2}^i - C_{m-2}^{j-m-1} \\
&\quad + 2C_{m-1}^{j-m-1} + \gamma_{2(m-1),j-1}^{(m-1)} - C_{m-2}^{j-m-1} \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^{2m-j-1} (-1)^{i+j} [C_{m-i-1}^{j-m-1} - C_{m-i-2}^{j-m-1}] C_{j-2}^i \\
&\quad + (-1)^{2m} C_{j-m-1}^{j-m-1} C_{j-2}^{2m-j} \\
&\quad + 2[C_{m-1}^{j-m-1} - C_{m-2}^{j-m-1}] + \gamma_{2(m-1),j-1}^{(m-1)} \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^{2m-j} (-1)^{i+j} C_{m-i-2}^{j-m-2} C_{j-2}^i + 2C_{m-2}^{j-m-2} + \gamma_{2(m-1),j-1}^{(m-1)} \\
&= \gamma_{2(m-1),j-2}^{(m-1)} + \gamma_{2(m-1),j-1}^{(m-1)}. \tag{13.24}
\end{aligned}$$

Similarly, this relation also holds when p is an odd number.

Correspondingly, to substitute $2m - p$ by j the expression in (13.20) becomes

$$\gamma_{2m,j}^{(m)} = \frac{j}{2m-j} C_{m-1}^{2m-j-1} = \frac{j}{m} C_m^{j-m}. \tag{13.25}$$

If it holds for $m = l - 1$ with $l \geq 5$ and every j with $l - 1 \leq j \leq 2(l - 1) - 1$, then it follows from (13.24) that

$$\begin{aligned}
\gamma_{2l,j}^{(l)} &= \frac{j-1}{l-1} C_{l-1}^{j-l} + \frac{j-2}{l-1} C_{l-1}^{j-l-1} \\
&= \frac{(j-1)(l-2)!}{(j-l)!(2l-j-1)!} - \frac{(j-2)(l-2)!}{(j-l-1)!(2l-j)!} \\
&= \frac{(l-2)!}{(j-l)!(2l-j)!} [(j-1)(2l-j) + (j-2)(j-l)] \\
&= \frac{(l-2)!}{(j-l)!(2l-j)!} (l-1)j = \frac{j}{l} C_l^{j-l},
\end{aligned}$$

and this indicates that (13.25) also holds for $m = l$ and every j with $l + 2 \leq j \leq 2l - 1$. So (13.25) holds for all $m \geq 5$ and $m + 2 \leq j \leq 2m - 1$.

In addition, for $m \geq 5$ and $j = m$ there is $\gamma_{2m,m}^{(m)} = 1 = m C_m^{m-m} / m$, and for $j = m + 1$ (that is, $p = m - 1$) there is

$$\begin{aligned}
\gamma_{2m,m+1}^{(m)} &= \gamma_{2m,m+1}^{(m-1)} - \gamma_{2m-1,m+1}^{(m-1)} \\
&= \gamma_{2m,2m-(m-1)}^{(m-1)} - [\gamma_{2m-1,2m-1-(m-2)}^{(m-2)} - \gamma_{2m-2,2m-2-(m-3)}^{(m-2)}] \\
&\quad \vdots \\
&= \sum_{i=0}^{m-2} (-1)^i \gamma_{2m-i,2m-i-(m-1-i)}^{(m-1-i)} + (-1)^{m-1} \gamma_{m+1,m+1}^{(1)} \\
&= \sum_{i=0}^{m-2} (-1)^i C_{m+1}^{i+2} + (-1)^{m-1} \chi_{m+1} \\
&= (1-1)^{m+1} - [C_{m+1}^0 - C_{m+1}^1 + (-1)^{m-1} C_{m+1}^{m+1}] + (-1)^{m-1} \chi_{m+1} \\
&= m + 1 - \chi_m \chi_{m+1} = m + 1 = \frac{m+1}{m} C_m^{m+1-m}.
\end{aligned}$$

These indicate that all the cases hold for (13.25) and it is the general formula for $\gamma_{2m,j}^{(m)}$ with $m \geq 1$ and $m \leq j \leq 2m - 1$. The following is the reformed version of *Theorem 13.1*.

Theorem 13.2. *The numbers $a_m, a_{m+1}, \dots, a_{2m}$ ($m \geq 1$) defined in Theorem 9.1 satisfy the relationship:*

$$\sum_{j=m}^{2m-1} (-1)^j \left[N_m^j \prod_{l=j+1}^{2m} d_l^* \right] a_j + 2a_{2m} = 0 \quad (13.26)$$

with $d_l^* = l + 1/2$ and

$$N_m^j = \frac{j}{m} C_m^{j-m} = \frac{j(m-1)!}{(j-m)!(2m-j)!},$$

which satisfies the iteration relation $N_m^j = N_{m-1}^{j-2} + N_{m-1}^{j-1}$ ($2 \leq m < j$).

14. To Prove $D_{1,n} \equiv 0$ and $D_{2,n} \equiv 0$

To trace back to (12.11), there is

$$D_{1,n} = \sum_{l=1}^n \sum_{k=l}^{2l} (-1)^{k-l} a_k \alpha_{k,2l-k} \beta_{k,n-l}$$

The distribution of the terms is shown in Figure 10.

It follows from (13.16) that the first one with $n = 1$ satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} D_{1,1} &= a_1 \alpha_{1,1} \beta_{1,0} - a_2 \alpha_{2,0} \beta_{2,0} \\ &= d_1 a_1 - a_2 = -\frac{1}{2} (-d_2^* a_1 + 2a_2) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (14.1)$$

with $d_1 = 1 + 1/4$ and $d_2^* = 2 + 1/2$.

14.1. To Prove $D_{1,n} \equiv 0$ for the Cases $2 \leq n \leq 4$

For all $l < k \leq 2l$ ($l \geq 1$) there is another expansion (the second expansion formula):

$$\beta_{k,q} = \beta_{l,q} - \sum_{j=1}^{q_0} \delta_{l,k}^{(j)} \beta_{k,q-j} \quad (14.2)$$

Figure 10: The distribution of the terms in $D_{1,n}$ with respect to k and l . The even terms with $k = 2m$ are marked by the symbol “*”, and the odd terms with $k = 2m - 1$ are marked by the symbol “o”. As an example, the case with $n = 32$ is shown here.

with $q_0 = \min\{q, k - l\}$, $\beta_{k,0} = 1$ and

$$\beta_{l,q} = \sum_{l+1 \leq i_n \leq K} \prod_{n=1}^q d_{i_n}^2, \quad \delta_{l,k}^{(j)} = \sum_{l+1 \leq i_n \leq k} \prod_{n=1}^j d_{i_n}^2.$$

For example, for the case with $n = 2$, in view of the results in (13.16) we get

$$\begin{aligned} D_{1,2} &= \sum_{l=1}^2 \sum_{k=l}^{2l} (-1)^{k-l} a_k \alpha_{k,2l-k} \beta_{k,2-l} \\ &= a_1 \alpha_{1,1} \beta_{1,1} - a_2 \alpha_{2,0} \beta_{2,1} \\ &\quad + a_2 \alpha_{2,2} \beta_{2,0} - a_3 \alpha_{3,1} \beta_{3,0} + a_4 \alpha_{4,0} \beta_{4,0} \\ &= (d_1 a_1 - a_2) \beta_{1,1} + \left[a_2 \left(\alpha_{2,2}^* + \delta_{1,2}^{(1)} \right) - a_3 \alpha_{3,1}^* + a_4 \right] \\ &= 0 \alpha_{1,2}^{(1)} + [(d_1 + d_2) d_2 a_2 - (d_1 + d_2 + d_3) a_3 + a_4] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} [d_3^* d_4^* a_2 - 3d_4^* a_3 + 2a_4] = 0, \end{aligned} \tag{14.3}$$

since $d_1 + d_2 = d_3^*$ and $d_1 + d_2 + d_3 = 3d_2 = 3d_4^*/2$. Here the deduction relation $\beta_{2,1} = \beta_{1,1} - \delta_{1,2}^{(1)} \beta_{2,0}$ is used. Similarly, for the case with $n = 3$,

$$\begin{aligned} D_{1,3} &= \sum_{l=1}^3 \sum_{k=l}^{2l} (-1)^{k-l} a_k \alpha_{k,2l-k} \beta_{k,3-l} \\ &= a_1 \alpha_{1,1} \beta_{1,2} - a_2 \alpha_{2,0} \beta_{2,2} \\ &\quad + a_2 \alpha_{2,2} \beta_{2,1} - a_3 \alpha_{3,1} \beta_{3,1} + a_4 \alpha_{4,0} \beta_{4,1} \\ &\quad + a_3 \alpha_{3,3} \beta_{3,0} - a_4 \alpha_{4,2} \beta_{4,0} + a_5 \alpha_{5,1} \beta_{5,0} - a_6 \alpha_{6,0} \beta_{6,0} \\ &= a_1 \alpha_{1,1} \beta_{1,2} - a_2 \alpha_{2,0} \left[\beta_{1,2} - \delta_{1,2}^{(1)} \beta_{2,1} \right] \\ &\quad + a_2 \alpha_{2,2} \beta_{2,1} - a_3 \alpha_{3,1} \left[\beta_{2,1} - \delta_{2,3}^{(1)} \beta_{3,0} \right] + a_4 \alpha_{4,0} \left[\beta_{2,1} - \delta_{2,4}^{(1)} \beta_{4,0} \right] \\ &\quad + a_3 \alpha_{3,3} \beta_{3,0} - a_4 \alpha_{4,2} \beta_{4,0} + a_5 \alpha_{5,1} \beta_{5,0} - a_6 \alpha_{6,0} \beta_{6,0} \\ &= (a_1 \alpha_{1,1} - a_2) \beta_{1,2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \left[a_2(\alpha_{2,2} + \delta_{1,2}^{(1)}) - a_3\alpha_{3,1} + a_4 \right] \beta_{2,1} \\
& + \left[a_3(\alpha_{3,3} + \alpha_{3,1}\delta_{2,3}^{(1)}) - a_4(\alpha_{4,2} + \delta_{2,4}^{(1)}) + a_5\alpha_{5,1} - a_6 \right] \\
= & 0\beta_{1,2} + 0\beta_{2,1} + a_3 \left[d_1d_2d_3 + d_3^2 \sum_{j=1}^3 d_j \right] \\
& - a_4 \left[d_1 \sum_{j=2}^4 d_j + d_2 \sum_{j=3}^4 d_j + d_3d_4 + (d_3^2 + d_4^2) \right] + a_5 \sum_{j=1}^5 d_j - a_6 \\
= & -\frac{1}{2}(-d_4^*d_5^*d_6^*a_3 + 4d_5^*d_6^*a_4 - 5d_6^* + 2a_6) = 0, \tag{14.4}
\end{aligned}$$

which is ensured by *Theorem 13.2*. Furthermore,

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{1,4} &= \sum_{l=1}^4 \sum_{k=l}^{2l} (-1)^{k-l} a_k \alpha_{k,2l-k}^* \beta_{k,4-l} \\
&= a_1\alpha_{1,1}\beta_{1,3} - a_2\alpha_{2,0}\beta_{2,3} \\
&\quad + a_2\alpha_{2,2}\beta_{2,2} - a_3\alpha_{3,1}\beta_{3,2} + a_4\alpha_{4,0}\beta_{4,2} \\
&\quad + a_3\alpha_{3,3}\beta_{3,1} - a_4\alpha_{4,2}\beta_{4,1} + a_5\alpha_{5,1}\beta_{5,1} - a_6\alpha_{6,0}\beta_{6,1} \\
&\quad + a_4\alpha_{4,4}\beta_{4,0} - a_5\alpha_{5,3}\beta_{5,0} + a_6\alpha_{6,2}\beta_{6,0} - a_7\alpha_{7,1}\beta_{7,0} + a_8\alpha_{8,0}\beta_{8,0} \\
&= a_1\alpha_{1,1}\beta_{1,3} - a_2\alpha_{2,0} \left[\beta_{1,3} - \delta_{1,2}^{(1)}\beta_{2,2} \right] \\
&\quad + a_2\alpha_{2,2}\beta_{2,2} - a_3\alpha_{3,1} \left[\beta_{2,2} - \delta_{2,3}^{(1)}\beta_{3,1} \right] \\
&\quad + a_4\alpha_{4,0} \left[\beta_{2,2} - \delta_{2,4}^{(1)}\beta_{4,1} - \delta_{2,4}^{(2)}\beta_{4,0} \right] + a_3\alpha_{3,3}\beta_{3,1} \\
&\quad - a_4\alpha_{4,2} \left[\beta_{3,1} - \delta_{3,4}^{(1)}\beta_{4,0} \right] + a_5\alpha_{5,1} \left[\beta_{3,1} - \delta_{3,5}^{(1)}\beta_{5,0} \right] \\
&\quad - a_6\alpha_{6,0} \left[\beta_{3,1} - \delta_{3,6}^{(1)}\beta_{6,0} \right] + a_4\alpha_{4,4}\beta_{4,0} \\
&\quad - a_5\alpha_{5,3}\beta_{5,0} + a_6\alpha_{6,2}\beta_{6,0} - a_7\alpha_{7,1}\beta_{7,0} + a_8\alpha_{8,0}\beta_{8,0} \\
&= (a_1\alpha_{1,1} - a_2)\beta_{1,3} \\
&\quad + \left[a_2(\alpha_{2,2} + \delta_{1,2}^{(1)}) - a_3\alpha_{3,1} + a_4 \right] \beta_{2,2} \\
&\quad + \left[a_3(\alpha_{3,3} + \alpha_{3,1}\delta_{2,3}^{(1)}) - a_4(\alpha_{4,2} + \delta_{2,4}^{(1)}) + a_5\alpha_{5,1} - a_6 \right] \beta_{3,1}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& +a_4(\alpha_{4,4} + \alpha_{4,2}\delta_{3,4}^{(1)} + \delta_{2,4}^{(1)}\delta_{3,4}^{(1)} - \delta_{2,4}^{(2)}) - a_5(\alpha_{5,3} + \alpha_{5,1}\delta_{3,5}^{(1)}) \\
& +a_6(\alpha_{6,2} + \delta_{3,6}^{(1)}) - a_7\alpha_{7,1} + a_8 \\
& = 0\beta_{1,3} + 0\beta_{2,2} + 0\beta_{3,1} + a_4(\alpha_{4,4} + \alpha_{4,2}\delta_{3,4}^{(1)} + \delta_{2,4}^{(1)}\delta_{3,4}^{(1)} - \delta_{2,4}^{(2)}) \\
& \quad -a_5(\alpha_{5,3} + \alpha_{5,1}\delta_{3,5}^{(1)}) + a_6(\alpha_{6,2} + \delta_{3,6}^{(1)}) - a_7\alpha_{7,1} + a_8 \\
& = \frac{1}{2} \left[\prod_{j=5}^8 d_j^* a_4 - 5 \prod_{j=6}^8 d_j^* a_5 + 9 \prod_{j=7}^8 d_j^* a_6 - 7d_8^* a_7 + 2a_8 \right] = 0. \quad (14.5)
\end{aligned}$$

Here the result in (13.16) together with the deduction relation

$$-a_4\alpha_{4,0}\delta_{2,4}^{(1)}\beta_{4,1} = -a_4\alpha_{4,0}\delta_{2,4}^{(1)}[\beta_{3,1} - \delta_{3,4}^{(1)}\beta_{4,0}]$$

are used.

14.2. To Prove the Cases $1 \leq k \leq 6$, $k = 2l$ and $k = 2l - 1$

For the general cases with $n \geq 5$, to choose $q = n - l$ then for $k \leq n$, there is always $k - l \leq n - l$ and $q_0 = \min\{k - l, n - l\} = k - l$, and on the contrary there is $q_0 = n - l$. So the defined region in **Figure 10** can be divided into 2 parts by the line $k = n$. Deriving in the form of the whole (with all l and all k) is extremely lengthy, so we give up this attempt and handle them column by column instead (to fix k).

It follows from (14.3)–(14.5) that the changes of the coefficients have consistency. In view of this, we write the final expression as

$$D_{1,n} = \sum_{l=1}^n (-1)^l E_l \beta_{l,n-l} \quad (14.6)$$

with

$$E_l = \sum_{k=l}^{2l} (-1)^k (\alpha_{k,2l-k} + \cdots) a_k := \sum_{k=l}^{2l} (-1)^k \mu_{2l,k} a_k, \quad (14.7)$$

which does not rely on the choice of n . Here the remainder terms are related to the times of deduction for different k .

Correspondingly, the expression in *Theorem 13.2* can be rewritten as

$$\sum_{k=l}^{2l} (-1)^k \lambda_{2l,k} a_k = 0 \quad (14.8)$$

with $\lambda_{2l,2l} = 2$, $\lambda_{2l,2l-1} = (2l-1)d_{2l}^*$ and for $l \leq k \leq 2l-2$

$$\lambda_{2l,k} = N_l^k \prod_{j=k+1}^{2l} d_j^* \quad (14.9)$$

with $N_l^k = kC_l^{k-l}/l$ and $d_j^* = j + 1/2$. Our goal is to prove $2\mu_{2l,k} = \lambda_{2l,k}$ for all $l \leq k \leq 2l$. According to the expansion strategy, the last two coefficients are untouched. One is trivially satisfied since $2\mu_{2l,2l} = 2 = \lambda_{2l,2l}$. Another is

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{2l,2l-1} &= \alpha_{2l-1,1} = \sum_{j=1}^{2l-1} d_j = \sum_{j=1}^{2l-1} (j + \frac{1}{4}) \\ &= (2l-1)(l + \frac{1}{4}) = \frac{1}{2}(2l-1)d_{2l}^* = \frac{1}{2}\lambda_{2l,2l-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (14.10)$$

So the left cases to be checked are $l \leq k \leq 2l-2$.

Notice that the values of $\mu_{2l,k}$ do not depend on the choice of n , to continue the deductions in (14.3)–(14.5) we see the first several columns [with same k ($\leq n$)] of it are

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{2,1} &= \alpha_{1,1} = d_1 = \frac{1}{2}d_2^*. \\ \mu_{2,2} &= \alpha_{2,0} = 1, \quad \mu_{4,2} = \alpha_{2,2} + \mu_{2,2}\delta_{1,2}^{(1)} = \frac{1}{2}d_3^*d_4^*. \\ \mu_{4,3} &= \alpha_{3,1} = d_1 + d_2 + d_3 = \frac{3}{2}d_4^*, \\ \mu_{6,3} &= \alpha_{3,3} + \mu_{4,3}\delta_{2,3}^{(1)} = \alpha_{2,2}d_3 + \frac{3}{2}d_4^*d_3^2 = \frac{1}{2}d_4^*d_5^*d_6^*. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mu_{4,4} &= \alpha_{4,0} = 1, \quad \mu_{6,4} = \alpha_{4,2} + \mu_{4,4}\delta_{2,4}^{(1)} = 2d_5^*d_6^*, \\
\mu_{8,4} &= \alpha_{4,4} + \mu_{6,4}\delta_{3,4}^{(1)} - \mu_{4,4}\delta_{2,4}^{(2)} = \frac{1}{2} \prod_{j=5}^8 d_j^*. \\
\mu_{6,5} &= \alpha_{5,1} = \frac{5}{2}d_6^*, \quad \mu_{8,5} = \alpha_{5,3} + \mu_{6,5}\delta_{3,5}^{(1)} = \frac{5}{2} \prod_{j=6}^8 d_j^*, \\
\mu_{10,5} &= \alpha_{5,5} + \mu_{8,5}\delta_{4,5}^{(1)} - \mu_{6,5}\delta_{3,5}^{(2)} = \frac{1}{2} \prod_{j=6}^{10} d_j^*. \\
\mu_{6,6} &= \alpha_{6,0} = 1, \quad \mu_{8,6} = \alpha_{6,2} + \mu_{6,6}\delta_{3,6}^{(1)} = \frac{9}{2}d_7^*d_8^*, \\
\mu_{10,6} &= \alpha_{6,4} + \mu_{8,6}\delta_{4,6}^{(1)} - \mu_{6,6}\delta_{3,6}^{(2)} = 3 \prod_{j=7}^{10} d_j^*, \\
\mu_{12,6} &= \alpha_{6,6} + \mu_{10,6}\delta_{5,6}^{(1)} - \mu_{8,6}\delta_{4,6}^{(2)} + \mu_{6,6}\delta_{3,6}^{(3)} = \frac{1}{2} \prod_{j=7}^{12} d_j^*. \quad (14.11)
\end{aligned}$$

It is easily checked that for the above mentioned k and l they all satisfy $\mu_{2l,k} = \lambda_{2l,k}/2$. To consider the cases with $k \geq 7$ we need to induce a general formula.

To denote $[(k+1)/2] = k_0$, then $\mu_{2k_0,k} = \alpha_{k,2k_0-k}$ equal to $\alpha_{k,0}$ in case k is even and equal to $\alpha_{k,1}$ in case k is odd. No matter k is even or odd, $\mu_{2k_0,k}$ is always the untouched one in the expansion process. The expansions in (14.11) have followed a specific rule:

$$\mu_{2l,k} = \alpha_{k,2l-k} + \sum_{j=1}^{l-k_0} (-1)^{j+1} \mu_{2(l-j),k} \delta_{l-j,k}^{(j)}, \quad (14.12)$$

which is a direct result of the second expansion formula. This iteration formula holds for $2 \leq k \leq n$ & $k_0+1 \leq l \leq k$ or $n < k < 2n$ & $k_0+1 \leq l \leq n$. In the following we make the proof by it.

14.3. To Prove the Case $k = l$ with Odd-Even Polynomials

Firstly, we make a transformation. To denote $p = 2l - k$ for simple, then it follows from (14.12) that

$$\begin{aligned}
\mu_{2l,k} &= \alpha_{k,p} + \mu_{2(l-1),k}(-1)^2\delta_{l-1,k}^{(1)} + \sum_{j=2}^{l-k_0} \mu_{2(l-j),k}(-1)^{j+1}\delta_{l-j,k}^{(j)} \\
&= \alpha_{k,p} + \alpha_{k,p-2}\delta_{l-1,k}^{(1)} \\
&\quad + \sum_{j=1}^{l-1-k_0} \mu_{2(l-1-j),k}(-1)^{j+1}\delta_{l-1-j,k}^{(j)}\delta_{l-1,k}^{(1)} + \sum_{j=2}^{l-k_0} \mu_{2(l-j),k}(-1)^{j+1}\delta_{l-j,k}^{(j)} \\
&= \alpha_{k,p} + \alpha_{k,p-2}\delta_{l-1,k}^{(1)} \\
&\quad + \sum_{j=2}^{l-k_0} \mu_{2(l-j),k} \left[(-1)^j \delta_{l-j,k}^{(j-1)} \delta_{l-1,k}^{(1)} + (-1)^{j+1} \delta_{l-j,k}^{(j)} \right] \\
&= \alpha_{k,p} + \alpha_{k,p-2}\delta_{l-1,k}^{(1)} + \alpha_{k,p-4} \left[\delta_{l-2,k}^{(1)} \delta_{l-1,k}^{(1)} - \delta_{l-2,k}^{(2)} \right] \\
&\quad + \sum_{j=3}^{l-k_0} \mu_{2(l-j),k} \left\{ (-1)^{j+1} \delta_{l-j,k}^{(j-2)} \left[\delta_{l-2,k}^{(1)} \delta_{l-1,k}^{(1)} - \delta_{l-2,k}^{(2)} \right] \right. \\
&\quad \left. + (-1)^j \delta_{l-j,k}^{(j-1)} \delta_{l-1,k}^{(1)} + (-1)^{j+1} \delta_{l-j,k}^{(j)} \right\} \\
&= \alpha_{k,p} + \alpha_{k,p-2}\delta_{l-1,k}^{(1)} + \alpha_{k,p-4} \left[\delta_{l-2,k}^{(1)} \delta_{l-1,k}^{(1)} - \delta_{l-2,k}^{(2)} \right] \\
&\quad + \alpha_{k,p-6} \left[\delta_{l-3,k}^{(1)} \delta_{l-2,k}^{(1)} \delta_{l-1,k}^{(1)} - \delta_{l-3,k}^{(1)} \delta_{l-2,k}^{(2)} - \delta_{l-3,k}^{(2)} \delta_{l-1,k}^{(1)} + \delta_{l-3,k}^{(3)} \right] \\
&\quad + \sum_{j=4}^{l-k_0} \mu_{2(l-j),k} \left\{ (-1)^j \delta_{l-j,k}^{(j-3)} \left[\delta_{l-3,k}^{(1)} \delta_{l-2,k}^{(1)} \delta_{l-1,k}^{(1)} - \delta_{l-3,k}^{(1)} \delta_{l-2,k}^{(2)} \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. - \delta_{l-3,k}^{(2)} \delta_{l-1,k}^{(1)} + \delta_{l-3,k}^{(3)} \right] + (-1)^{j+1} \delta_{l-j,k}^{(j-2)} \left(\delta_{l-2,k}^{(1)} \delta_{l-1,k}^{(1)} - \delta_{l-2,k}^{(2)} \right) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + (-1)^j \delta_{l-j,k}^{(j-1)} \delta_{l-1,k}^{(1)} + (-1)^{j+1} \delta_{l-j,k}^{(j)} \right\} \\
&= \dots
\end{aligned} \tag{14.13}$$

The above calculations can be simplified by adopting a new combinatorial number (the sum of all the possible products):

$$\rho_{l,k,m} = \sum_{0 \leq i_j \leq j, i_m \neq 0} (-1)^{m+\chi_i} \prod_{j=1}^m \delta_{l-j,k}^{(i_j)}, \quad (14.14)$$

here χ_i is the number of nonzero elements in i_1, i_2, \dots, i_m with respect to the i -th products. There is also an additional definition $\delta_{l-j,k}^{(0)} \equiv 1$ for all possible l, j and k . With the help of it, the above deduction process can be continued. Finally, we get the general formula below:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{2l,k} &= \alpha_{k,p} + \alpha_{k,p-2} \rho_{l,k,1} + \alpha_{k,p-4} \rho_{l,k,2} + \dots + \alpha_{k,2k_0-k} \rho_{l,k,l-k_0} \\ &= \sum_{m=0}^{l-k_0} \alpha_{k,p-2m} \rho_{l,k,m} \end{aligned} \quad (14.15)$$

with $p = 2l - k$, $k_0 = [(k+1)/2]$ and $\rho_{l,k,0} \equiv 1$.

This formula is not simple, either. Yet it is suitable for the particular case with $l = k$. At this time, the coefficients are easily gotten. The first 3 are

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{k,k,1} &= \delta_{k-1,k}^{(1)} = d_k^2, \\ \rho_{k,k,2} &= \delta_{k-2,k}^{(1)} \delta_{k-1,k}^{(1)} - \delta_{k-2,k}^{(2)} = (d_{k-1}^2 + d_k^2) \rho_{k,k,1} - d_{k-1}^2 d_k^2 = d_k^4, \\ \rho_{k,k,3} &= \delta_{k-3,k}^{(1)} \delta_{k-2,k}^{(1)} \delta_{k-1,k}^{(1)} - \delta_{k-3,k}^{(1)} \delta_{k-2,k}^{(2)} - \delta_{k-3,k}^{(2)} \delta_{k-1,k}^{(1)} + \delta_{k-3,k}^{(3)} \\ &= \delta_{k-3,k}^{(1)} \rho_{k,k,2} - \delta_{k-3,k}^{(2)} \rho_{k,k,1} + \delta_{k-3,k}^{(3)} \\ &= (d_{k-2}^2 + d_{k-1}^2 + d_k^2) d_k^4 - (d_{k-2}^2 d_{k-1}^2 + d_{k-2}^2 d_k^2 + d_{k-1}^2 d_k^2) d_k^2 \\ &\quad + d_{k-2}^2 d_{k-1}^2 d_k^2 = d_k^6. \end{aligned}$$

By this kind of iteration relation we get the general result $\rho_{k,k,m} = d_k^{2m}$.

Hence,

$$\mu_{2k,k} = \alpha_{k,k} + \alpha_{k,k-2} d_k^2 + \alpha_{k,k-4} d_k^4 + \dots + \alpha_{k,2k_0-k} d_k^{2(k-k_0)}. \quad (14.16)$$

Furthermore, we have two explicit expressions:

$$k = 2k_0 : \mu_{2k,k} = \sum_{m=0}^{k_0} \alpha_{k,2m} d_k^{k-2m},$$

$$k = 2k_0 + 1 : \mu_{2k,k} = \sum_{m=1}^{k_0} \alpha_{k,2m-1} d_k^{k-2m+1}.$$

To consider the generating function below:

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &= (x + d_1)(x + d_2) \cdots (x + d_k) \\ &= \alpha_{k,0} x^k + \alpha_{k,1} x^{k-1} + \alpha_{k,2} x^{k-2} + \alpha_{k,3} x^{k-3} + \cdots \\ &\quad + \alpha_{k,k-2} x^2 + \alpha_{k,k-1} x + \alpha_{k,k} \\ &= \sum_{m=0}^{k_0} \alpha_{k,2m} x^{k-2m} + \sum_{m=1}^{k_0} \alpha_{k,2m-1} x^{k-2m+1} \end{aligned} \quad (14.17)$$

with $\alpha_{k,0} = 1$. In view of $(-d_k + d_k) = 0$, we have $f(-d_k) = 0$ and there is always

$$\sum_{m=0}^{k_0} \alpha_{k,2m} d_k^{k-2m} = \sum_{m=1}^{k_0} \alpha_{k,2m-1} d_k^{k-2m+1}$$

no matter k is even or odd. Hence,

$$\mu_{2k,k} = \frac{1}{2} f(d_k) = \frac{1}{2} \prod_{i=1}^k (d_k + d_i) = \frac{1}{2} \prod_{j=k+1}^{2k} d_j^* = \frac{1}{2} \lambda_{2k,k}. \quad (14.18)$$

The left work is to prove $\mu_{2l,k} = \lambda_{2l,k}/2$ for the cases with $k \geq 7$ and $l + 1 \leq k \leq 2l - 2$.

14.4. To Prove with AI Software

The expression of (14.12) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{2l,k} &= \alpha_{k,p} + \sum_{j=1}^{l-k_0} (-1)^{j+1} \mu_{2(l-j),k} \delta_{l-j,k}^{(j)} \\ &= \alpha_{k,p} + \sum_{j=k_0}^{l-1} (-1)^{l-j+1} \mu_{2j,k} \delta_{j,k}^{(l-j)}, \end{aligned} \quad (14.19)$$

where k_0 is the integer part of $(k + 1)/2$,

$$\alpha_{k,p} = \sum_{1 \leq i_n \leq k} \prod_{n=1}^p d_{i_n}, \quad \delta_{j,k}^{(q)} = \sum_{j+1 \leq i_n \leq k} \prod_{n=1}^q d_{i_n}^2$$

with $p = 2l - k$, $q = l - j$ and $d_{i_n} = i_n + 1/4$. The related positive-integer numbers satisfy: $2 \leq k \leq n$ & $k_0 + 1 \leq l \leq k$ or $n < k < 2n$ & $k_0 + 1 \leq l \leq n$ (see Figure 10). To assume

$$\mu_{2j,k} = \frac{1}{2} N_j^k \prod_{i=k+1}^{2j} d_i^* = \frac{k(j-1)!}{2(k-j)!(2j-k)!} \prod_{i=k+1}^{2j} d_i^* \quad (14.20)$$

with $d_j^* = j + 1/2$ holds for all $k_0 \leq j \leq l - 1$, we prove it also holds for $j = l$.

This iteration formula is involved in calculating $\alpha_{k,p}$ and $\delta_{j,k}^{(q)}$. The most feasible approach is to adopt artificial-intelligence (AI) softwares. For arbitrary given k, j, p and q , to obtain general formulas for $\alpha_{k,p}$ and $\delta_{j,k}^{(q)}$ we have tried some of them but failed (provide no algorithm). Perhaps we haven't found an advanced one or the way of asking questions needs improvement. To provide detailed algorithms may be helpful.

For specific numbers with $2 \leq p \leq 4$ and $1 \leq q \leq 2$ some of the AI softwares work and yield the following results:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{k,2} &= \frac{1}{2^2} C_k^2 \left(k^2 + \frac{8}{3}k + \frac{23}{12} \right), \\ \alpha_{k,3} &= \frac{1}{2^3} C_k^3 \left(k + \frac{3}{2} \right) \left(k^2 + 2k + \frac{5}{4} \right), \\ \alpha_{k,4} &= \frac{1}{2^4} C_k^4 \left(k^4 + 4k^3 + \frac{35}{6}k^2 + \frac{19}{5}k + \frac{247}{240} \right), \\ \delta_{j,k}^{(1)} &= \frac{1}{3}(k^3 - j^3) + \frac{3}{4}(k^2 - j^2) + \frac{23}{48}(k - j), \\ \delta_{j,k}^{(2)} &= \frac{1}{2} [\delta_{j,k}^{(1)}]^2 - \left[\frac{1}{10}(k^5 - j^5) + \frac{3}{8}(k^4 - j^4) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{23}{48}(k^3 - j^3) + \frac{15}{64}(k^2 - j^2) + \frac{247}{7680}(k - j) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (14.21)$$

Furthermore, there are

$$\begin{aligned}
\mu_{k+2,k} &= \alpha_{k,2} + \mu_{k,k} \delta_{k/2,k}^{(1)} \\
&= \frac{k(k-1)}{8} \left(k^2 + \frac{8}{3}k + \frac{23}{12} \right) + 1 \cdot k \left(\frac{7}{24}k^2 + \frac{9}{16}k + \frac{23}{96} \right) \\
&= \frac{k^2}{8} \left(k^2 + 4k + \frac{15}{4} \right) = \frac{k^2}{8} d_{k+1}^* d_{k+2}^* = \frac{1}{2} \lambda_{k+2,k}. \\
\mu_{k+3,k} &= \alpha_{k,3} + \alpha_{k,1} \delta_{(k+1)/2,k}^{(1)} \\
&= \frac{k(k-1)(k-2)}{48} d_{k+1}^* \left(k^2 + 2k + \frac{5}{4} \right) \\
&\quad + \frac{k}{2} d_{k+1}^* \cdot \frac{k-1}{96} (28k^2 + 70k + 45) \\
&= \frac{k(k-1)}{48} d_{k+1}^* \left(k^3 + 7k^2 + \frac{59}{4}k + \frac{35}{4} \right) \\
&= \frac{(k+1)k(k-1)}{48} d_{k+1}^* d_{k+2}^* d_{k+3}^* = \frac{1}{2} \lambda_{k+3,k}. \\
\mu_{k+4,k} &= \alpha_{k,4} + \mu_{k+2,k} \delta_{k/2+1,k}^{(1)} - \mu_{k,k} \delta_{k/2,k}^{(2)} \\
&= \frac{k(k-1)(k-2)(k-3)}{2^4 \cdot 4!} \left(k^4 + 4k^3 + \frac{35}{6}k^2 + \frac{19}{5}k + \frac{247}{240} \right) \\
&\quad + \frac{k^2}{8} d_{k+1}^* d_{k+2}^* \cdot \frac{k-2}{96} (28k^2 + 86k + 75) \\
&\quad - 1 \cdot \frac{k(k-2)}{92160} (20k^2 + 42k + 19)(196k^2 + 290k + 39) \\
&= \frac{k(k-2)}{2^4 \cdot 4!} \cdot \frac{k(k+2)}{16} (2k+3)(2k+5)(2k+7)(2k+9) \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \frac{k}{k/2+2} C_{k/2+2}^4 \prod_{j=k+1}^{k+4} d_j^* = \frac{1}{2} \lambda_{k+4,k}. \tag{14.22}
\end{aligned}$$

That is, the cases with $k = 2l - 2, 2l - 3, 2l - 4$ are proved.

From the above results we see that the calculation of $\alpha_{k,p}$ becomes more and more complex along with the increasing of p . The expression of $\delta_{j,k}^{(q)}$ is more complex than that of $\alpha_{k,p}$.

For convenience of other researchers to continue exploring, we provide an

algorithm below.

By employing the generating function we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{m=0}^k \alpha_{k,m} x^{k-m} &= \prod_{i=1}^k (x + d_i) = \prod_{i=1}^k \left(x + \frac{1}{4} + i\right) \\
&= \sum_{r=0}^k S_{k,r} \left(x + \frac{1}{4}\right)^{k-r} \\
&= \sum_{r=0}^k S_{k,r} \sum_{m=0}^{k-r} C_{k-r}^m \frac{1}{4^m} x^{k-r-m} \\
&= \sum_{r=0}^k S_{k,r} \sum_{m=r}^k C_{k-r}^{m-r} \frac{1}{4^{m-r}} x^{k-m} \\
&= \sum_{m=0}^k \left[\sum_{r=0}^m \frac{1}{4^{m-r}} C_{k-r}^{m-r} S_{k,r} \right] x^{k-m}, \tag{14.23}
\end{aligned}$$

which results in

$$\alpha_{k,p} = \sum_{r=0}^p \frac{1}{4^{p-r}} C_{k-r}^{p-r} S_{k,r}, \tag{14.24}$$

where

$$S_{k,r} = \sum_{1 \leq i_1 \leq \dots \leq i_r \leq k} \prod_{n=1}^r i_n$$

(with $S_{k,0} = 1$) is the elementary-symmetric sum, which means to choose r elements from $1, 2, 3, \dots, k$, multiply them and sum up all the product.

It follows from the Newton's identity that (with $1 \leq r \leq k$):

$$S_{k,r} = \frac{1}{r} \sum_{i=1}^r (-1)^{i-1} S_{k,r-i} T_{k,i}, \tag{14.25}$$

here $T_{k,i} = \sum_{m=1}^k m^i$ (with $T_{k,0} = k$) is the power-symmetric sum, which is known for the cases $1 \leq i \leq 3$:

$$T_{k,1} = \frac{k(k+1)}{2}, \quad T_{k,2} = \frac{k(k+1)(2k+1)}{2}, \quad T_{k,3} = \frac{k^2(k+1)^2}{4}.$$

For the cases with $4 \leq i \leq k$ it can be calculated by

$$T_{k,i} = \frac{1}{i+1} \sum_{u=0}^i C_{i+1}^u B_u k^{i+1-u}, \quad (14.26)$$

where B_u is the Bernoulli number which satisfy $\sum_{u=0}^i C_{i+1}^u B_u = 0$. $B_0 = 1$, $B_1 = -1/2$ and all the other odd terms are 0.

With the help of the above iteration relations the coefficient $\alpha_{k,p}$ can be calculated. With respect to $\delta_{j,k}^{(q)}$, its corresponding polynomial is

$$G_j(x) = \prod_{i=1}^{k-j} (x - d_{j+i}^2) = \sum_{m=0}^{k-j} (-1)^m \delta_{j,k}^{(m)} x^{k-m}. \quad (14.27)$$

The Newton's identity reads

$$U_{k-j,q} = \frac{1}{q} \sum_{i=1}^q (-1)^{i-1} U_{k-j,q-i} V_{k-j,i} \quad (14.28)$$

with $U_{k-j,q} = \delta_{j,k}^{(q)}$ ($q \leq k-j$), in which

$$\begin{aligned} V_{k-j,i} &= \sum_{m=1}^{k-j} (d_{j+m}^2)^{2i} = \sum_{m=1}^{k-j} \left(j + m + \frac{1}{4} \right)^{2i} \\ &= \sum_{m=1}^{k-j} \sum_{r=0}^{2i} C_{2i}^r (j+m)^r \frac{1}{4^{2i-r}} \\ &= \sum_{r=0}^{2i} \frac{1}{4^{2i-r}} C_{2i}^r \sum_{m=1}^{k-j} (j+m)^r \\ &= \sum_{r=0}^{2i} \frac{1}{4^{2i-r}} C_{2i}^r \left[\sum_{m=1}^k m^r - \sum_{m=1}^j m^r \right] \\ &= \sum_{r=0}^{2i} \frac{1}{4^{2i-r}} C_{2i}^r (T_{k,r} - T_{j,r}). \end{aligned} \quad (14.29)$$

Hence, all the $\delta_{j,k}^{(q)}$ with $k_0 \leq j \leq l-1$ and $1 \leq q \leq l-k_0$ can be calculated by iteration, and the relation (14.19) can be checked by AI softwares.

14.5. The Anticipated Results

What we mainly anticipate is the result below:

Proposition 14.1. *(need to be proved) For $l \geq 1$ the number $\mu_{2l,k}$ defined in (14.7) has explicit expressions as follows:*

$$\mu_{2l,k} = \frac{1}{2} N_l^k \prod_{j=k+1}^{2l} d_j^*, \quad l \leq k \leq 2l - 1 \quad (14.30)$$

and $\mu_{2l,2l} = 1$ with $d_j^* = j + 1/2$ and

$$N_l^k = \frac{k}{l} C_l^{k-l} = \frac{k(l-1)!}{(k-l)!(2l-k)!}.$$

Furthermore, to insert the value of $\mu_{2l,k}$ into (14.7) we get

$$\begin{aligned} E_l &= \sum_{k=l}^{2l-1} (-1)^k \left[\frac{1}{2} N_l^k \prod_{j=k+1}^{2l} d_j^* \right] a_k + a_{2l} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \sum_{k=l}^{2l-1} (-1)^k \left[N_l^k \prod_{j=k+1}^{2l} d_j^* \right] a_k + 2a_{2l} \right\} = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (14.31)$$

where the equality in Theorem 13.2 is used. So the expression in (14.6) is identical 0, and the derived result is as follows:

Corollary 14.1. *For all $1 \leq n \leq K - [K/2] - 1$, the coefficients defined in (12.11) satisfies*

$$D_{1,n} = \sum_{l=1}^n \sum_{k=l}^{2l} (-1)^{k-l} a_k \alpha_{k,2l-k} \beta_{k,n-l} \equiv 0.$$

Similarly, for the case with $K - [K/2] \leq n \leq K - 1$ we write $D_{2,n}$ as

$$D_{2,n} = \sum_{l=1}^{K-n} \sum_{k=l}^{2l} (-1)^{k-l} a_k \alpha_{k,2l-k} \beta_{k,n-l}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{l=1}^{K-n} (-1)^l \left[\sum_{k=l}^{2l} (-1)^k a_k \mu_{2l,k} \right] \beta_{l,n-l} \\
&= \sum_{l=1}^{K-n} (-1)^l E_l \beta_{l,n-l}, \tag{14.32}
\end{aligned}$$

then the relation for E_l in (14.31) also holds, and we have another corollary:

Corollary 14.2. *For all $K - [K/2] \leq n \leq K - 1$, the coefficients defined in (12.11) satisfies*

$$D_{2,n} = \sum_{l=1}^{K-n} \sum_{k=l}^{2l} (-1)^{k-l} a_k \alpha_{k,2l-k} \beta_{k,n-l} \equiv 0.$$

15. The Final Expression of $A_K(z)$

Based on the above two Corollaries, we simplify the expressions in (12.11) and (12.12) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{1}{2} A_K(z) &= \sum_{n=1}^{K-n_0-1} (-1)^{K-n} D_{1,n} z^{2(K-n)} \\
&\quad + \sum_{n=K-n_0}^{K-1} (-1)^{K-n} D_{2,n} z^{2(K-n)} \\
&\quad + \sum_{n=K-n_0}^K (-1)^{K-n} D_{3,n} z^{2(K-n)} \\
&= 0 + 0 + \sum_{n=0}^{n_0} (-1)^n D_{3,K-n} z^{2n} \tag{15.1}
\end{aligned}$$

with $n_0 = [K/2]$ and

$$D_{3,K-n} = \sum_{l=n+1}^{K-n} \sum_{k=l}^{n+l} (-1)^{k-l} a_k \alpha_{k,2l-k} \beta_{k,K-n-l}. \tag{15.2}$$

For the even case with $K = 2n_0$, the term about $n = n_0$ vanishes since $\sum_{l=n+1}^{K-n} = \sum_{l=n_0+1}^{n_0} = 0$. The defined terms in $D_{3,K-n}$ are shown in Figure 11. In addition, for the initial case with $n = 0$ they form a diagonal line $k = l$ with $1 \leq l \leq K$, and for the last case with $K = 2n_0 + 1$ and $n = n_0$ they form a horizontal line $l = n_0 + 1$ with $n_0 + 1 \leq k \leq K$.

Figure 11: The distribution of the terms in $D_{3,K-n}$ with respect to k and l . As an example, the case with $n = 20$ and $K = 60$ are shown here.

The expression of $D_{3,K-n}$ needs to be simplified.

16. The Thought of Final Proof

For the case with $|\varepsilon| \leq 1/4$ and $b \neq 0$ it follows from (15.1) that

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{4} A_K(s) A_K(\bar{s}) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{n_0} (-1)^n D_{3,K-n} (\varepsilon + bi)^{2n} \cdot \sum_{n=0}^{n_0} (-1)^n D_{3,K-n} (\varepsilon - bi)^{2n} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{n=0}^{n_0} (-1)^n D_{3,K-n} \sum_{r=0}^{2n} C_{2n}^r \varepsilon^{2n-r} (bi)^r \\
&\quad \cdot \sum_{n=0}^{n_0} (-1)^n D_{3,K-n} \sum_{r=0}^{2n} C_{2n}^r \varepsilon^{2n-r} (-bi)^r \\
&= \left[\sum_{n=0}^{n_0} (-1)^n D_{3,K-n} \sum_{p=0}^n C_{2n}^{2p} \varepsilon^{2n-2p} (bi)^{2p} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \sum_{n=1}^{n_0} (-1)^n D_{3,K-n} \sum_{p=1}^n C_{2n}^{2p-1} \varepsilon^{2n-2p+1} (bi)^{2p-1} \right] \\
&\quad \cdot \left[\sum_{n=0}^{n_0} (-1)^n D_{3,K-n} \sum_{p=0}^n C_{2n}^{2p} \varepsilon^{2n-2p} (bi)^{2p} \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \sum_{n=1}^{n_0} (-1)^n D_{3,K-n} \sum_{p=1}^n C_{2n}^{2p-1} \varepsilon^{2n-2p+1} (bi)^{2p-1} \right] \\
&= \left[\sum_{n=0}^{n_0} (-1)^n D_{3,K-n} \sum_{p=0}^n C_{2n}^{2p} \varepsilon^{2n-2p} (bi)^{2p} \right]^2 \\
&\quad - \left[\sum_{n=1}^{n_0} (-1)^n D_{3,K-n} \sum_{p=1}^n C_{2n}^{2p-1} \varepsilon^{2n-2p+1} (bi)^{2p-1} \right]^2 \\
&= \left[\sum_{n=0}^{n_0} \sum_{p=0}^n (-1)^{n+p} D_{3,K-n} C_{2n}^{2p} \varepsilon^{2n-2p} b^{2p} \right]^2 \\
&\quad + \varepsilon^2 b^2 \left[\sum_{n=1}^{n_0} \sum_{p=1}^n (-1)^{n+p-1} D_{3,K-n} C_{2n}^{2p-1} \varepsilon^{2n-2p} b^{2p-2} \right]^2 \\
&:= P_K(\varepsilon, b)^2 + \varepsilon^2 b^2 Q_K(\varepsilon, b)^2. \tag{16.1}
\end{aligned}$$

For the even case with $K = 2n_0$ there is $D_{3,K-n_0} = 0$.

Notice that for $b = 0$ there is always $\xi(1/2 + \varepsilon + 0i) > 0$ in (3.3) and that $P_K(\varepsilon, b)^2 \geq 0$ for all $|\varepsilon| \leq 1/4$ and $b \neq 0$, to prove *Proposition 11.1* it only needs to show that $Q_K(\varepsilon, b) \neq 0$ for all $0 < |\varepsilon| \leq 1/4$, $b \neq 0$ and a large enough K . In addition, the zero points on the critical line $\sigma = 1/2$ can be

approximated by the solutions of

$$0 = P_K(0, b) = \sum_{n=0}^{n_0} (-1)^n D_{3, K-n} b^{2n} \quad (16.2)$$

for a large enough K (according to the original definition, there is $\varepsilon^0 = 1$).

To exchange the summation orders of n and p it results in

$$\begin{aligned} Q_K(\varepsilon, b) &= \sum_{n=1}^{n_0} \sum_{p=1}^n (-1)^{n+p-1} D_{3, K-n} C_{2n}^{2p-1} \varepsilon^{2n-2p} b^{2p-2} \\ &= \sum_{p=1}^{n_0} \sum_{n=p}^{n_0} (-1)^{p+n-1} D_{3, K-n} C_{2n}^{2p-1} \varepsilon^{2n-2p} b^{2p-2} \\ &= \sum_{p=1}^{n_0} \left[\sum_{n=0}^{n_0-p} (-1)^{n+1} D_{3, K-n-p} C_{2(n+p)}^{2p-1} \varepsilon^{2n} \right] b^{2p-2} \\ &:= \sum_{p=1}^{n_0} R_p(\varepsilon) b^{2p-2}. \end{aligned} \quad (16.3)$$

It only needs to prove that $R_p(\varepsilon)$ maintains its sign unchanged for all $1 \leq p \leq n_0$ and $0 < |\varepsilon| \leq 1/4$.

References

- [1] New Scientist(2018) Has the Riemann hypothesis been solved? <https://www.newscientist.com/section/news/>
- [2] Titchmarsh, E.C. (1986) The Theory of the Riemann Zeta-Function. 2nd Edition, Edited and with a Preface by Heath-Brown, D.R., The Clarendon Press, Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- [3] Edwards, H.M. (1974) Riemann's Zeta Function. Academic Press, Waltham. (Reprinted by Dover Publications, Mineola, 2001).

- [4] Borwein, P., Choi, S., Rooney, B. and Weirathmueller, A. (2007) *The Riemann Hypothesis: A Resource for the Afficionado and Virtuoso Alike*. Springer Press, New York. [https:// doi.org /10.1007 /978-0-387-72126-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-72126-2)
- [5] Lu, C.H. (2016) *Ramble on the Riemann Hypothesis*. Tsinghua University Press, Beijing, 20-38. (In Chinese)
- [6] Devlin, K.J. (2003) *The Millennium Problems: The Seven Greatest Unsolved Mathematical Puzzles of Our Time*. Basic Books, New York, 19-60.
- [7] Riemann, B. (1998) *On the Number of Prime Numbers Less than a Given Quantity*. Translated by Wilkins, D.R. [http:// www. claymath. org/ library/ historical/ riemann/english/1.pdf](http://www.claymath.org/library/historical/riemann/english/1.pdf)
- [8] Riemann, B. (2016) *The Collected Works of Bernhard Riemann. Vol. 1, Chinese Edition*, Translated by Li, P.L., Higher Education Press, Beijing, 127-135.
- [9] E Bombieri (2000) *Problems of the Millennium: The Riemann Hypothesis*. [http:// www.claymath.org/ millennium-problems/ riemann-hypothesis](http://www.claymath.org/millennium-problems/riemann-hypothesis)
- [10] Lune, J., Riele, J.J. and Winter, D.T. (1986) *On the Zeros of the Riemann Zeta Function in the Critical Strip, IV*. *Mathematics of Computation*, **46**, 667-681. <https://doi.org/10.1090/S0025-5718-1986-0829637-3>

- [11] Gourdon, X. (2004) The 10^{13} first zeros of the Riemann zeta function, and zeros computation at very large height. <http://numbers.computations.free.fr/Constants/Miscellaneous/zetazeros1e13-1e24.pdf>
- [12] Stein, E.M. and Shakarchi, R. (2003) Princeton Lectures in Analysis I: Fourier Analysis, An Introduction. Princeton University Press, Princeton.
- [13] Stein, E.M. and Shakarchi, R. (2003) Princeton Lectures in Analysis II: Complex Analysis. Princeton University Press, Princeton.
- [14] Kudryavtseva, A.E., Saidak, F. and Zvengrowski, P. (2005) Riemann and His Zeta Function. *Morfismos*, **9**, 1-48.
- [15] Selberg, A. (1942) On the zeros of the zeta-function of Riemann, *Norske Vid. Selsk. Forh. Trondhjem*, **15**, 59-62.
- [16] Levinson, N. (1974) More than one-third of the zeros of the Riemann zeta-function are on $\sigma = 1/2$, *Advances in Mathematics*, **13**, 383–436. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0001-8708\(74\)90074-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0001-8708(74)90074-7)
- [17] Conrey, J.B. (1989) More than Two Fifths of the Zeros of the Riemann Zeta Function Are On the Critical Line. *Journal für die reine und angewandte Mathematik*, No. 399, 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1515/crll.1989.399.1>
- [18] Odlyzko, A. (2025) Tables of Zeros of the Riemann Zeta Function. https://www-users.cse.umn.edu/~odlyzko/zeta_tables/index.html.